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Enterprise data governance and data ownership models: developing an Ownership Model Implementation Tool (OMIT)

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Studies: Information Sciences

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Abstract

The importance of effective usage of data seems to be embraced by a continuously growing number of organisations. With effective usage of data comes the significance of data management/governance and a transitioning approach of these practices from an enterprise perspective. Within data governance, (data) ownership models, sometimes termed stewardship models, are gaining ground as a concept. While data management and governance are gaining popularity within organisations, these fields are scientifically still in their infancy, leading to a lacking body of existing knowledge and practical tools to be used during the design and implementation of governance structures, like ownership models, resulting in a variety of practical challenges.

Deploying a design science research approach (DSR), this research proposes a scientifically validated practical tool to be used by organisations during the design, implementation and/or (further) development of ownership models, termed as Ownership Model Implementation Tool (OMIT). During research phase one, through a literature review and semi-structured interviews with participants from five organisations, central data governance and ownership model practices were explored, as well as related practical challenges encountered by organisations. This resulted in a conceptual model serving as the basis for the OMIT. During research phase two, the first OMIT was developed and validated through semi-structured interviews with six experts in the field of data management and enterprise architecture. This resulted in the final OMIT, allowing organisations to self-assess their current ownership model practices and further design, implement and improve an ownership model implementation.

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1. Introduction

The importance of data to organisations in all sectors became evident over the past decades and is now widely embraced. This is supported by the fact that many (larger) organisations increasingly view data as a key asset and embrace data management as one of their key components (van Gils, 2020). The immense and continuous growth of data in the world and the vast increase of Big Data practices make evident why organisations are acknowledging the need for proper data management (Statista Research Department, 2022a). One of the capabilities paramount to data management is data governance. The question of how to properly govern data and how to design the organisation in a way that enables doing so has been elaborated on widely (Tallon et al., 2013; Henderson, 2017; Abraham et al., 2019). A relatively recent trend within organisations is the transition to an enterprise perspective of data management and data governance (Jonker et al., 2012). Oftentimes data within organisations was and still is contained in siloed, compartmentalised and disparate information systems (Jonker et al., 2012; Stedman, 2021). Practice has shown that as organisations grow, along with the aforementioned accumulation of data, challenges arise for data management and data governance within these organisations (Jonker et al., 2012; Harrison et al., 2018; Schilling et al., 2020). This explains the widespread transition towards approaching data management from an enterprise perspective, which involves an organisation-wide view of structuring data management and information systems (Harrison et al., 2018; Tableau, n.d.).

Considering data governance practices, data ownership is among the most well-established of data governance concepts (Van Alstyne et al., 1995; Khatri & Brown, 2010; Otto 2011a; DAMA, 2017). Related to this is a popular data governance model that has found its way into many (larger) organisations. This model is a role-based data governance model described by van Gils (2020) as ‘ownership/stewardship models’, hereafter called ‘ownership models’. Although varying per organisation, the implementation of such an ownership model generally involves assigning certain agents the roles of ‘Data Owner’, ‘Data Stewards’ and ‘Data User’ (van Gils, 2020). These roles aim to establish a basis for the coordination of data governance activities. For example, the Data Owner is essentially accountable for the specific dataset under his/her management. The description of the Data Owner role, in turn, contains this person’s tasks, responsibilities and accountabilities related to the data under management (van Gils, 2020).

Although data governance and related concepts, like ownership models (van Gils, 2020), are gaining in popularity (Henderson, 2017), it remains a relatively new field both in practice and in academic research (van Gils, 2020; Aarnoutse, 2021). Next to that, the recent transition within many organisations towards an enterprise perspective of data governance practices causes organisations to encounter difficulties related to their ownership model implementations, ranging from decreasing performance of Data Owners (Personal communication, January 28, 2022; February 24, 2022), data quality issues, efficiency issues and, eventually, higher costs (Personal communication, September 19, 2022; Personal communication, September 30, 2022). The early stages of academic research into data governance, on top of the early stages in which practical handling of data governance still resides, lead many organisations to wade into uncharted waters

when implementing governance practices. Professionals do of course possess their (practical) expertise accumulated throughout their careers and some formal frameworks and practical tools related to data governance can be found. The DAMA-DMBOK is most prominent among data management frameworks (Henderson, 2017) and some practical tools related to data governance can be found in the form of Data Governance Maturity Models (DGMMs) (Merkus, 2015; Firican, n.d.) and RA(S)CI-matrices (Henderson, 2017). A DGMM can be a useful tool for organisations to get a baseline measure of data governance maturity, enabling (further) implementation and improvement of its governance practices. However, rightfully noted by Merkus (2015) and Comuzzi and Patel (2016), these practical tools are almost exclusively based on best practices by firms and lack scientific substantiation and validation, raising questions about their internal validity and generalisability. This can potentially be troubling for organisations looking to utilise such a model, thus increasing the necessity for a scientifically validated practical tool. Moreover, where DGMMs as a concept are potentially useful for organisations, the vast majority of these models lack the necessary specificity and concrete tools for organisations to accurately self-assess their data governance maturity levels (Marchildon et al., 2018). Furthermore, while a widely adopted practical tool to assist in the assignment of accountabilities, responsibilities and activities exists in the form of RA(S)CI-matrices, practical tools specifically designed to utilise during the design and (further) implementation of ownership models do, to the author's knowledge, not exist.

To summarise, scientific research into data governance and ownership models remains in its infancy, accompanied by a lack of scientifically verified practical tools for ownership model design and implementation. Furthermore, the growing number of organisations transitioning to enterprise data governance makes the development of a scientifically validated practical tool for organisations to be used during (further) implementation of ownership models from an enterprise perspective a research topic of considerable interest and relevance. Based on this, the central problem during the research is formulated as follows: *'A lack of existing scientifically validated practical tools to be used during the design and (further) implementation of ownership models complicates developing and/or implementing such ownership models in an optimal manner for many organisations, leading to a variety of practical challenges.'*

This research addresses the central problem by aiming to fulfil the following research goals:

- 1) Exploring the presence and characteristics, both empirically and in existing literature, of challenges concerning ownership model implementations from an enterprise perspective.
- 2) Developing and proposing a scientifically validated practical tool to be used by organisations during (further) design and/or implementation of ownership models, termed by the author as an Ownership Model Implementation Tool (OMIT), incorporating a high level of concreteness and specificity to allow self-assessment by organisations.

Concerning the first research goal, primary data was collected by conducting interviews to further substantiate the relevance of the research at hand. There was a strong indication present in existing literature for the necessity and demand by organisations of practical data governance tools, as argued above (Merkus, 2015; Comuzzi & Patel, 2016; Henderson, 2017; Firican, n.d.). However, further grounding this indication through empirical research and, thus, incorporating several organisations in the context of the research should strengthen the basis of the research. Furthermore, it helps to establish the contextual foundation of the research, substantiates the relevance of the research and strengthens the generalisability of the findings and, hence, of the resulting practical tool.

The contributions of the research are manifold for both scholars and practitioners. First, this research adds to the scarce body of available academic work on data governance in general and ownership models more specifically. Second, by developing what the author terms as the OMIT, a first draft towards a scientifically validated practical tool aiming to assist organisations in the design and/or implementation of an ownership model is provided. This developed OMIT is of great potential use and relevance to practitioners that are looking to design and/or implement an ownership model. Finally, by pioneering the scientific establishment of this practical tool, the research provides guidance both in method and content to other scholars conducting research in related fields.

The remainder of this chapter has the following structure. The following section firstly elaborates on the (construction of) research questions. Thereafter, a detailed description of the overarching research design is provided to clarify the design choice for the research.

1.1 Research questions

The research was divided into two phases during which the aforementioned research goals were fulfilled. The division of the research into two phases follows from the adoption of a Design Science Research (DSR) approach (Hevner, 2007) as the overarching research design. A more detailed description of this approach is provided in the following section. During phase one, the following set of main research question (i.e. Main RQ) and sub-questions (SQs) was answered. Questions were constructed using the research paper by Thuan et al. (2019) for guidance:

Main RQ1: What conceptual basis can be established to assist in developing the OMIT, to address the challenges organisations face when developing and implementing ownership models?

SQ1: What are the definitions and characteristics of central concepts for ownership models and related data management/governance practices?

SQ2: How can challenges generally encountered by organisations related to ownership models be described?

SQ3: How can differences in organisational ownership model maturity be described?

SQ4: What existing practical tools can be identified that could assist in the development of an OMIT?

SQ5: What are relevant ownership model characteristics that need to be considered by organisations when implementing ownership models?

Answering these questions, through an extensive literature review and interviews, both aimed to fulfil the first research goal and aimed to lay the basis for the fulfilment of the second research goal. Following phase one, the next step was to continue with the design phase of the research (Hevner, 2007), which was also phase two of the research. The following set of main RQ and SQs were answered during the second phase of the research. Questions were again constructed using the research paper by Thuan et al. (2019) for guidance:

Main RQ2: How can an empirically validated OMIT be developed to address the challenges organisations face when developing and implementing ownership models?

SQ6: What concrete ownership model dimensions can be identified that need to be included in the OMIT?

SQ7: What concrete supportive questions can be formulated for the OMIT to enable self-assessment by organisations?

SQ8: What do experts in the field of data governance deem an appropriate OMIT to enable addressing the challenges organisations face when developing and implementing ownership models?

By answering these questions, firstly, the initial version of the OMIT could be established based on the phase one literature review and interviews. Secondly, by answering these questions through several expert-validation interviews during phase two of the research, the final OMIT could be established. This OMIT can be utilised by organisations while designing and (further) implementing their ownership model and related practices

2. Methodology

This section contains a description of the methodology during the research. First, a discussion of the adopted DSR approach as the overarching research design is provided. Second, the research setting is described. Third, the methods and processes of data collection are discussed, including an elaboration on the construction of interview questions and topics. Finally, the methods and processes of data analysis are presented.

2.1 Design Science approach (DSR-approach)

The adopted overarching research design is based on Design Science Research (DSR) (Hevner et al., 2004; Hevner, 2007; Hevner & Chatterjee, 2010). It is 'overarching' in the sense that it does not describe the methods of data collection and analysis, but serves as a higher-level design choice regarding the sequencing of iterations of data collection/analysis and construction of the OMIT. An elaboration is provided here to educate the reader on the design choices that were made.

DSR finds its origin in the field of information system (IS) research (Hevner et al., 2004). Thuan et al. (2019) find that DSR is mainly used for problem-solving type research. This aligns with Hevner et al. (2004) and Hevner (2007), saying that DSR is pragmatic in nature and is mostly used where new (IT) artefacts are created and existing artefacts are improved. These characteristics fit the research at hand well based on the development of the OMIT (i.e. a new artefact) during this research, explaining the decision to adopt a DSR approach. The adopted approach in the current research was based on Hevner's (2007) three-cycle view of DSR. These three cycles of DSR are the relevance cycle, design cycle and rigour cycle, as shown in figure 1. A more detailed description of this approach is given below, accompanied by important sidenotes related to where the adopted design deviates from Hevner's (2007) three-cycle view of DSR.

Figure 1. Three cycles of Design Science Research (Hevner, 2007).

The relevance cycle concerns the stipulation of the environment in which the research is conducted (Hevner, 2007). The environment consists of the organisation(s) that are experiencing a certain challenge and the people and (technical) systems within these organisations. Within this cycle, the challenge in need of being addressed is established (Hevner et al. 2004). Solving the central challenge is addressed in the design cycle, discussed hereafter, by improving an existing or developing a new artefact. Field testing, conducted in the research environment, then serves to evaluate whether the artefact is perceived as successful.

Whether or not the outcome is perceived as successful commonly determines if multiple iterations through these cycles are necessary. While for technical IS/IT improvements it is manageable to go through multiple iterations time and resource-wise, it was less so for the research at hand, where multiple organisations were included in the research and field testing required these organisations to put in time and resources for each iteration. Hence, the research at hand was restricted in the sense that only a limited number of iterations were possible.

The rigour cycle, perhaps similar to a 'common' literature review, consists of, and serves to establish, a base of existing knowledge to draw from throughout the subsequent cycles. It consists of existing related (scientific) theories and methods, the experience and expertise of people situated in the research environment and the relevant existing artefacts in the research environment (Hevner et al., 2004; Hevner, 2007). Establishing the knowledge base and doing so rigorously ensures that the new or improved artefact is not some routine adaptation of existing artefacts, but is instead innovative and therefore contributing to the knowledge base as well. A sound execution thus partially ensures a contribution to the (academic) knowledge base, inherently important for scientific research. Moreover, it contributes to the organisation(s) in the research environment in the sense that it partially ensures a novel artefact is delivered, implying relevance to practitioners (Hevner, 2007).

Established DSR is often conducted in an environment specific to a certain information system or single organisation. This implies that the rigour cycle differs from established DSR. This did not by any means diminish the usefulness of the adopted DSR approach for the current research, nor did it diminish the usefulness of the research results. On the contrary, the fact that multiple organisations were included in this research only increases the generalisability of the results; an important part of scientific research. However, it remains important for the reader to bear in mind that, and how, the adopted research design differs from common DSR.

The design cycle constitutes the very core of the research in more established DSR. During this cycle, the new or improved artefact is constructed. In practice, this implies the construction, evaluation and subsequent adaptations/refinements of the artefact according to feedback obtained during this sequence (Hevner, 2007).

Hevner (2007) discusses that during the design cycle, rapid iterations are made between the construction of the artefact, evaluation and feedback incorporation. Considering what Hevner (2007) says, it is important to bear in mind that DSR is mostly applied in the applied/technical domain of IS/IT. Hevner for example mentions:

“... that artefacts must be rigorously and thoroughly tested in laboratory and experimental situations before releasing the artefact into field testing along the relevance cycle. This calls for multiple iterations of the design cycle in design science research before contributions are output into the relevance cycle and the rigor cycle.” (Hevner, 2007, p. 91).

Considering the research at hand, this way of working was simply not feasible or perhaps not even possible. Within the current research, laboratory and/or experimental testing was not an option; we are not (re)running programmable scenarios/algorithms, but validating an artefact (i.e. the OMIT) by consulting experts *in the field*. Hence, iterations between artefact construction and evaluation demanded moving to and from the design cycle and relevance cycle more rapidly than common in established DSR papers. Following this, the design- and relevance cycle of the research were much more intertwined than they were separate cycles as is common in established DSR.

2.2 Research setting

The author had initially been in contact with a Dutch national bank to conduct a sequel to the research by Aarnoutse (2021). The organisation noticed that certain Data Owners had lower performance compared to other Data Owners. This was initially ascribed to the differing characteristics of the data under ownership. Better performing Data Owners had ownership of enterprise data, while lesser performing Data Owners had ownership of more siloed data. A variety of internal reasons prevented this research from happening. In the process of constructing a research proposal, however, initial literature and conversations with practitioners indicated that challenges related to ownership model implementations from an enterprise perspective are both current and pressing, to both scholars and practitioners, in more than just a singular organisation. This led to the current research topic and to the aim of establishing a practical tool for ownership model design and implementation from an enterprise perspective: the OMIT.

The research lasted for a little over a year, with the majority of the work conducted during the last nine months. During phase one of the research, the focus was to establish a conceptual basis for the development of the OMIT. To do so, the aim was to question several different organisations on their current data management/governance and ownership model practices. To find participants, the author reached out directly to certain employees of eight different organisations based on a referral. These organisations were in an ongoing transition to data governance from an enterprise perspective, said to have data ownership-related challenges and had differing levels of data governance maturity. Moreover, the organisations with a lower data governance maturity were all in the process of either creating a roadmap for implementation or were implementing an ownership model. Furthermore, the organisations were situated across a

variety of industries, both public and private, which was ought to increase the generalisability of the results.

Reaching out led to the inclusion of five organisations in the research. An overview of these organisations, their characteristics and the function and years of experience of the interviewees can be found in table 1. Years of experience were based on career paths shown on LinkedIn.

Type of organisation	Industry	No. Employees	Function/role	Experience
1. Municipality	Public sector	2400	Strategic CIO advisor and quartermaster	13 years
2. University of applied sciences	Education	4000	Enterprise Architect	11 years
3. Educational publisher & umbrella holding company	Publishing (hard copy and software)	300 & 5000	Senior manager analytics and enterprise architect	19 years
4. Government agency – monitoring and safekeeping	Public sector	2700	Senior advisor data governance and data architect	13 years
5. Distribution Network Operator (DNO)	Electricity distribution (privatised)	6000	Data domain manager and Architect / Architecture manager	13 years

Table 1. Overview of organisations and interviewees – research phase one.

Both the organisations and employees were anonymised in this writing. Numbers were provided for each organisation to ease later referrals. As the functions of interviewees show, the author spoke to employees that were well known with both the data governance situation within the organisation as well as the desired and intended developments related to data governance. This implied speaking to employees in a (near) strategic function that regularly spoke to the executive level of the organisation.

During phase two of the research, after phase one and the fulfilment of the first research goal, the focus was on validating the initial OMIT based on certain dimensions, discussed in more detail in section 2.3.3. To do so, the aim was to conduct several expert validation interviews with several experts in the field of data management/governance and (enterprise) architecture. A LinkedIn message was used to ask for participation, which yielded a response from four new participants. Moreover, the author approached two participants that had already been interviewed during phase one (interviewees two and three in table 1, repeated in table 2 for clarity), leading to a total of six experts that were interviewed during phase two of the research. An overview of the participants during phase two of the research can be found in table 2.

Type of organisation	Industry	No. Employees	Function/role	Experience
2. University of applied sciences	Education	4000	Enterprise Architect	11 years
3. Educational publisher & umbrella holding company	Publishing (hard copy and software)	300 & 5000	Senior manager analytics and enterprise architect	19 years

Main function/role	Experience	Recent contributions and activities
6. Head of organisation's Data Management department	10+ years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementing Data Management on an enterprise-wide level for a publicly listed multinational organisation.
7. Founder and director of an organisation specialised in data & analytics services for digital transformations.	20+ years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Besides current company activities a track record in Business Intelligence and Data & Analytics consulting. Board activities in a renowned data management foundation.
8. Managing partner at an organisation specialised in supporting organisations in digital transformations.	15+ years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Besides current company activities a track record in consulting, research and coaching, all around bridging the fields of IT and business. Board activities in a renowned data management foundation. University professor in related fields. Author of several books in the field of data management and enterprise architecture.
9. Currently self-employed. Advisor in data management, focussing on coaching/training of professionals and consulting services.	25+ years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Besides current activities a vast track record in consulting on several projects and in roles, such as senior data officer, senior advisor and data architect. Board activities in a renowned data management foundation.

Table 2. Overview of interviewees and their professional background – research phase two.

While the interviews during phase one specifically aimed to question the status quo of ownership model practices within organisations, interviews during phase two of the research specifically aimed to validate the developed OMIT based on expert knowledge of interviews. Therefore, the expertise of the interviewees was of considerable importance during phase two of the research. As indicated in table 2, all experts had a proven track record in the field of data management, data governance and/or enterprise architecture through a variety of contributing factors. The author therefore deemed the combination of these factors more than suitable to establish that participants were in fact 'experts'.

2.3 Method and process of data collection

2.3.1 Data collection: phase one

As noted earlier, the research was divided into two phases. During phase one, the starting point was to conduct a literature review to construct a basic understanding of the research concepts, such as the meaning of data, data governance, the concept of ownership and data ownership, differing perspectives of data management/governance and ownership models. This part of the literature review, found in sections 3.1 to 3.5, served to answer SQ1. Furthermore, the literature review served as a starting point to gain the necessary knowledge to answer SQ2 and to research how differing ownership model maturities could be established to answer SQ3. Moreover, the literature review served to gather existing knowledge to build upon when constructing the conceptual basis for the OMIT, the latter meaning relevant ownership model topics and content for the OMIT. To do so, first, SQ4 was answered, found in section 3.6.1. Further gathering this existing literature enabled partially answering SQ5. This partial answer based on existing literature can be found in section 3.6.2. Finally, considering the entire literature review, gathered information served as input for the establishment of the phase one and phase two interview questions, therefore contributing to the primary data collection during the research.

Collected data ranged from academic papers, white papers, books written by data management and governance experts and expert blogs/opinions. In collecting literature of varying nature the author aimed to apply data triangulation to increase the validity and reliability of the findings. By researching the background and credentials of authors of informal sources for expert knowledge and their link to academics the author tried to uphold the reliability of source content. Keywords that were used during information retrieval were, among others, (enterprise) data management, (enterprise) data governance, data stewardship, data ownership, stewardship models, (data) ownership models, data silos, data governance frameworks, maturity model(s) and data governance maturity models. Next to retrieving literature by querying search engines the author also retrieved relevant literature by using a snowballing technique and getting referrals by people in the research environment to relevant articles and books.

Following the literature review, a total of five interviews were conducted. These interviews firstly aimed to further ground the relevance of the research in practice. Moreover, these phase one interviews enabled answering SQ2 and SQ3. Furthermore, the interviews allowed to conclude the answer to SQ5, combining the now-gathered primary data and priorly collected secondary data during the literature review. By using both primary and secondary data the author applied methodological triangulation to further increase the validity and reliability of the results. Interviews were semi-structured, meaning that topics, questions and a rough questioning sequence were prepared while allowing for deviations and follow-up questions where deemed appropriate. Interview questions related to formal descriptions of governance practices and ownership model implementations. Where these concepts were less or not yet developed, questions were adapted for informal procedures or ways of working. Next to that, questions related to the organisation's vision on the (further) development of its ownership model and/or

its future implementation. Doing so allowed to gain insights into the differing ownership model maturities organisations had (SQ3) as well as establishing relevant ownership model characteristics (SQ5). Finally, interview questions concerned ownership model-related issues encountered in practice (SQ2). The construction of the interview topic list and questions is discussed in the following section.

Participants in the interviews stemmed from the five organisations described earlier in table 1. These interviews consisted of three interviews with two experts and two solo interviews. All but one interview lasted roughly an hour, while the other lasted roughly half an hour. The scope of the research did not allow to speak to more organisations. However, the author noticed that saturation of the findings began to occur while analysing the final interview. Therefore, this relatively small number of organisations was ought to provide grounds for generalisability of the results at least to some extent. All interviews were conducted in Dutch and, hence, interview questions were also prepared in Dutch. Interviews were conducted online through Microsoft Teams and were recorded, after gaining permission, using OBS studio software. Interviews were transcribed verbatim, in the sense that conversations were transcribed as originally spoken. This means that the speaker's grammar, wording and chosen sentence structure were not altered in the transcripts. However, communicative details such as stutters, pauses, non-spoken sounds, etc., were not included. Transcribing yielded a total of 73 pages to be analysed. Next to that, two out of five organisations provided internal documents regarding the organisations' data governance structure, including its ownership model and roadmap for their enterprise architecture.

The choice for a qualitative research approach and, accordingly, semi-structured interviews was rather obvious. Qualitative research lends itself to explore and expose connections among certain factors and how these connections lead to certain patterns or occurrences (Bleijenbergh, 2016). Furthermore, qualitative research is an ideal method for research topics that lack a large existing base of available knowledge and are therefore exploratory in nature (Boeije, 2010). Primary data in this research consisted entirely of personal experiences from experts within organisations. It therefore has highly subjective properties that require the interpretations and exploration that a qualitative research approach allows. Moreover, using a semi-structured interview style allowed respondents to deviate and elaborate on aspects that they deemed important. Furthermore, the lack of existing research in this direction shows the exploratory properties of the research. Altogether, this shows that a qualitative research approach and semi-structured interviews were the only suitable approach to adopt.

2.3.2 Constructing phase one interview topics and questions

Based on the initial literature review, a list of relevant recurring content was devised to establish the relevant topics for the phase one interviews. Following that, topics were further divided into sub-topics as a basis for the construction of interview questions. Besides the initial literature review, initial communications preceding the interviews of the research (Personal communication, January 28, 2022; February 24, 2022) contributed in establishing these topics and subtopics as well. A visualisation of the established topics is displayed in figure 2.

Figure 2. Central topics and subtopics used to construct interview questions and topic list.

In figure 2, the top two topics are the central concepts utilised to construct interview questions. While data ownership in itself is a relevant concept to this research and a separate concept compared to the 'Data Owner'-role within an ownership model, this distinction was not made as emphatically during the interviews. Discussing ownership model implementations in general automatically led to the discussion of Data Owners and data ownership. Therefore, discussing data ownership as a separate concept was not deemed relevant during the interviews while during the literature review, this distinction was made more explicitly. By questioning the organisations about their current ownership model implementations, according to the topics shown in the diagram, insights were gained both into the ownership model maturity of the organisation (SQ3) and into what the organisations deem to be relevant characteristics of ownership models (SQ5). Subsequently, enquiries were at first made into encountered practical challenges directly related to the two central concepts. Next to that, indications of practical challenges stemming from organisational aspects other than the aforementioned central concepts were also pursued and asked upon. Together, this led to insights into data governance and ownership model-related challenges of the organisations (SQ2).

2.3.3 Data collection: phase two

The start of the second phase of the research involved the development of the OMIT. Constructing the first version of the OMIT essentially constituted answering SQ6 and SQ7, based on the findings during phase one of the research (i.e. SQ1 to SQ5). Zooming in on SQ8 and main RQ2, the author considered how to establish an OMIT that expert practitioners deem appropriately addresses the challenges organisations face when developing and implementing ownership models. By designing the OMIT for organisations to assist in their transition to enterprise data governance while accounting for the differing organisational ownership model maturities, the author argues the OMIT appropriately addresses the challenges organisations face when developing and implementing ownership models. Furthermore, the author argues that the OMIT should be

perceived as practically useable, relevant and effective. After the initial OMIT had been constructed, the next step was to scrutinise and validate the initial OMIT based on its practical useability, relevance and effectiveness. Validating the OMIT in this scientifically appropriate manner allowed the formulation of an answer to SQ8. Furthermore, this validation round enabled the construction of the second and final OMIT version which, in turn, enabled answering the final RQ2 and enabled fulfilling the second research goal.

In order to validate the OMIT, the author conducted another six semi-structured interviews with experts in data management, data governance and (enterprise) architecture which were shown earlier in table 2. These interviews were all one-on-one interviews, similar to the adopted methodology by Merkus (2015), Comuzzi and Patel (2016) and Marchildon et al. (2018). These researchers rightfully note that one-on-one interviews might induce the interviewee(s) to speak more freely and allow the interviewer to devote all attention to one person, thus enabling full focus on both answers and non-verbal signals, therefore making it easier to ask follow-up questions. Moreover, interviews with a single expert require the interviewer to only consider an individual professional background per interview, preventing potential conflicting backgrounds and views. Combining these points simply implies one-on-one interviews allow a more controllable environment compared to a group-style validation session.

By incorporating both new experts (4) and experts (2) who had already been involved in the phase one interviews, the author aimed to balance the positive effects of having experts with a fresh outlook and having experts already familiar with the specific research context and content. The former helped in strengthening generalisability to other contexts. Moreover, the former helped reduce potential bias towards the content by already interviewed experts, stemming from their prior involvement in the content and initial OMIT construction. The latter strengthens the validity of the results in that prior participants were now able to assess whether the developed OMIT, based on their inputs during phase one, is consistent with their inputs during phase one and, hence, validly developed.

The content of the phase two interview questions was based on a combination of the topics discussed by Marchildon et al. (2018) during the demonstration and evaluation phase of their model development. Due to the limited scope of this research, the author was unable to adopt a similar approach of going through multiple rounds of validation nor was it possible to request participants to make a test assessment of the OMIT. Especially the latter aspect weakens the results to a certain extent, as it meant that participants were asked to provide their feedback based on their conception of how the OMIT would be in practice, rather than providing feedback on how it actually performed. Nevertheless, with their vast expertise, the author deemed the participants more than capable to form a realistic image of how the OMIT would perform in practice. Moreover, by combining the topics discussed by Marchildon et al. (2018) during their several validation rounds it was possible to scrutinise the initial OMIT on the most crucial aspects in a single validation round. The interviews started by validating the ease of use and clarity of the OMIT. This included discussing the clarity of used terminology, wording, dimensions, concrete questions and instruction sheet within the OMIT. Furthermore, participants were asked about their perception

of the OMIT's overall ease of use and how well/easy questions were answerable. Following this, the OMIT's practical relevance and effectiveness were validated. This amounted to asking the opinion of participants regarding several aspects of the OMIT, such as its completeness (e.g. potential omissions and redundancy of content), perceived relevance for the intended practitioners, perceived effectiveness and usefulness of the OMIT in enabling self-assessment and perceived effectiveness and usefulness of the OMIT in facilitating ownership model design and implementation.

Interviews lasted one and a half hours. Next to that, participants were provided with the initial OMIT, as shown in appendix A, one week before the interviews and were requested to spend half an hour browsing through and scrutinising the OMIT beforehand. All interviews were again conducted in Dutch. However, the OMIT was provided to participants in the 'original form' (i.e. in English). Interviews were again conducted through Microsoft Teams, recorded using OBS studio software and transcribed in the same verbatim manner as for the phase one interviews. Moreover, the author made extensive notes during the phase two interviews with specific remarks of participants for later referral and to ease the process of making adjustments to the initial OMIT.

2.4 Data analysis

2.4.1 Data analysis: phase one

Coding was deployed to structure and analyse the interview transcripts during phase one. Atlas.ti qualitative research software was used to capture the transcripts and to subsequently code the primary data in a systemic manner. Sources obtained and analysed during the literature review throughout the different phases of the research were not included in the coding process.

A coding process as described by Boeije (2010) can be divided into three parts: open coding, axial coding and selective coding. Coding in this manner is consistent with a grounded theory approach to analysing data (Boeije, 2010). However, when coding according to grounded theory it is common to start with a blank slate and let the themes and concepts emerge from the data. While the author allowed unanticipated themes and concepts to emerge from the data, relevant characteristics of ownership models were established based on the initial literature review for which the author looked while collecting and, subsequently, coding the primary data. Therefore, during phase one of the research, coding was done consistent with a hybrid version of grounded theory and framework analysis while lending its terminology (i.e. open- and axial-coding) from grounded theory (Boeije, 2010). Besides ascribing open codes and axial codes to the data, in-vivo coding was applied to highlight interesting terminology used by participants that captured occurrences essential to ownership model characteristics. An example was an interviewee that used the term 'data-debt' (*data schuld*) to illustrate the inefficiency and resulting higher costs from inconsistent and manifold datasets, systems and interfaces that essentially concerned the same data instance. Another example was an interviewee using the term 'coalition of the willing' when describing actively seeking employees that are intrinsically engaged with informal governance practices to start fulfilling more formal governance roles and, finally, using the term 'fear of missing out' to describe the feeling agents surrounding the 'coalition of the

willing' get once they notice formal governance practices pay off, after which they want to join as well. These concepts are explained and elaborated on in chapter 4, where the interview findings are discussed.

Since there is no need to look for causality in the current research, the exploration of what causes certain phenomena and the related interrelationships between factors is of lesser importance. Therefore, open coding and, subsequently, axial coding sufficed. The former (i.e. open coding) involved the initial attribution of meaning to a textual fragment according to the author's interpretation, while the latter (i.e. axial coding) involved further assigning open codes to a higher-level category, theme or concept as to, eventually, identify emerging common themes and concepts. The coding process was an iterative process, as creating axial codes also involved moving back and forth between open codes and axial codes, further refining open codes, merging codes that were more or less similar and so on. The resulting codebook concerning the phase one interviews can be found in appendix C.

The iterative coding process can be illustrated by using the open codes '(un)availability of money for performing data governance practices' (*'(on)beschikbaarheid van geld voor uitvoeren data governance activiteiten'*) and '(un)availability of time for performing governance practices' (*'(on)beschikbaarheid van tijd voor uitvoeren data governance activiteiten'*) as an example. While it seems obvious that available resources are important for performing governance practices, this characteristic did not emerge from the literature review and, hence, was open-coded in a manner consistent with grounded theory since it emerged from the primary data itself as an essential characteristic for data governance practices. Initially, these codes were described by separating 'time' and 'money' as distinct resources. However, as coding progressed and while turning back to prior codes, the author realised that in the business context of the organisations time often equals money, thus merging the initial open codes into a new code '(un)availability of resources for performing data governance practices' (*'(on)beschikbaarheid van middelen voor uitvoeren data governance activiteiten'*).

Subsequently, illustrating axial coding further on in the coding process, the author noticed that the lack of available resources for data governance practices was a recurring issue encountered by multiple organisations in the research environment. Therefore, the aforementioned open code regarding the lack of available resources was linked to the higher level theme (i.e. axial code) 'Challenges/problems related to ownership model/governance framework implementations', stemming from the author's interpretation that the lack of an available overarching formal governance board or enterprise data governance budget results in certain challenges.

Furthermore, the author noticed that open-coded topics could be categorised in terms of an organisational level of abstraction. Certain topics took place in the higher hierarchical levels of the organisation, like policy establishment. Other topics took place in the lower hierarchical levels of the organisation, like actively searching for Data Owners. In line with this the author constructed the higher level axial codes 'Executive/Macro-level organisational/managerial aspects of ownership models' (*'Executive/Macro-level organisatie/management aspecten van*

ownership modellen') and 'Managerial/Micro-/Meso-level organisational/managerial aspects of ownership models' (*Managerial/Micro-/Meso-level organisatie/management aspecten van ownership modellen*') to which certain open codes were allocated.

The analysis continued in this manner until no additional codes or code-refinements were deemed necessary anymore, implying theoretical saturation had been reached. At that point what followed was the constructed conceptual model shown in chapter 4, serving as a basis for the initial OMIT development. Due to the restricted scope of the research, it was not feasible to take additional measures, such as peer debriefing or coding together with a peer, to improve the intercoding coherence and overall validity and reliability of the data analysis. This is an important caveat that the reader should bear in mind while considering the research.

2.4.2 Data analysis: phase two

While the content of the phase one interviews allowed well for open coding and, subsequently, further assigning open codes to higher-level axial codes, this was the case to a lesser extent for the phase two interviews. Considering the phase one interviews, they served to establish a conceptual model containing higher-level categories/dimensions of central ownership model characteristics. These central ownership model characteristics in the conceptual model were based on specific occurrences and practices related to the ownership model activities and choices within the interviewed organisations. This allowed for open coding of the specific ownership model occurrences/practices and, when higher level categories were identified, further assigning these to higher level axial codes. Contrarily, the phase two interviews served the more practical purpose of adjusting and refining specific aspects of the OMIT. The interviews during phase two therefore yielded rather structured and specific feedback related to specific aspects of the initial OMIT, like concerns related to the content of an individual question or the clarity of a provided definition in the OMIT, which could then be adjusted almost directly. The author noticed while transcribing the interviews that it was rather easy to address the feedback from participants by referring back to the extensive notes made during the interviews, combined with referring back to the interview transcripts when the notes were somewhat unclear or were lacking the necessary details. Following this, it was deemed unnecessary to code the transcripts in the same extensive manner as during phase one. Therefore, the interview transcripts were only segmented into content-related remarks, remarks related to clarity/ambiguity of OMIT aspects and arguments related to the effectiveness and usefulness of the OMIT. This minimal form of segmenting was done to ease referring back when deemed necessary and to create structure in the design process for the second OMIT version. Next to this form of segmenting, when similarities and interlinkages were found among the remarks of participants, these remarks were highlighted to indicate they were potentially more important to address compared to other remarks where a single interviewee made a remark. Subsequently, the redefining and further designing of the second OMIT version commenced almost step-by-step according to the specific remarks in the interview notes and, where necessary, by consulting the segments and highlights in the interview transcripts.

3. Literature review

This chapter contains a review of the relevant literature and a discussion of central concepts and definitions that were utilised during both research phases. Most of the central concepts require proper defining and elaboration at the same time. Therefore, all central concepts are defined and discussed in their own subsection. First, 'data' as a construct is discussed accompanied by an illustration of the assumed meaning of data during the research. Second, an elaboration is provided regarding the characterisations of data governance along with a stipulation of the research's scope related to data governance. Third, the general concept of 'ownership' and, thereafter, 'data ownership' is discussed and elaborated on. Fourth, the concepts of 'enterprise data' and 'siloes data', stemming from the ongoing transition towards enterprise data governance, are defined and further elaborated on. Fifth, ownership model(s) are reviewed based on existing literature. Finally, to facilitate constructing the OMIT, a review of existing practical tools related to data governance practices and ownership model implementations is provided, along with a stipulation of relevant dimensions for the OMIT.

3.1 What is data?

Before considering what can be defined as data governance, it is important to establish what can be understood when talking about 'data' in the first place. This notion is important to consider as not all readers have the same construct in mind when considering the meaning of 'data'. The seemingly age-old discussion of 'what is data?' and 'what is information?' immediately springs to mind when considering the definition of 'data' provided in the Oxford Dictionary: "Facts or information, especially when examined and used to find out things or to make decisions." (Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, n.d.). Considering that 'data' under this definition is understood to be 'information', it becomes clear that what might be commonly understood as 'data' falls short of the important caveat that data and information are not the same. This caveat can best be made clear using the DIKW (Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom) pyramid as an illustration (Rowley, 2007), shown in figure 3, of which the bottom layers are most relevant for this discussion.

Figure 3. DIKW (Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom) pyramid (Rowley, 2007).

According to Rowley (2007), data in itself does not (yet) have meaning and therefore does not allow the user, be it an organisation or a single individual, to base decisions on it. Data, from this viewpoint, can be described as (a collection of) physical and factual observations that are yet to be processed and analysed, are therefore unorganised and do not convey any specific meaning (Rowley, 2007). Once the user performs some kind of analysis of the data, providing semantics, information is obtained. However, as inferred from the DAMA-DMBOK (Henderson, 2017) and van Gils (2020), a hierarchical representation like this implies that factual observations (i.e. data) emerge without prior information or knowledge. This is hardly possible, as the mere establishment of what is observed to be a factual happening requires having some information or knowledge concerning the observation. In fact: "... the two concepts [data and information] are intertwined with and dependent on each other. Data is a form of information and information is a form of data." (Henderson, 2017, ch. 2, section 2.2). This refinement illustrates the central construct of 'data' and 'information' adopted during the research and commonly held in the IS and data governance field.

3.2 Data governance

Noted by many scholars, a common definition of 'data governance' is hard to come by (Benfeldt et al., 2019). The DAMA-DMBOK, which can be seen as the golden standard in data management and governance, defines data governance as: "... the exercise of authority and control (planning, monitoring, and enforcement) over the management of data assets." (Henderson, 2017, ch. 3, section 1). The author argues that this definition fails to incorporate the multifaceted characterisation of data governance as a discipline and organisational capability. As noted by Weber et al. (2009), data governance, being a subset of corporate governance, combines notions from IT- and business-driven perspectives. It therefore does not solely concern technical- or system-related aspects but also business- and organisational issues (Weber et al., 2009). Gregory (2011) further illustrates the diverse range of organisational aspects that data governance is concerned with, saying that it relates to more than just privacy or regulatory compliance, security or data quality, but encompasses all of the above and more. Data governance practices then, in line with the aforementioned definition in the DAMA-DMBOK, involve 'governance-matters' similar to corporate governance, like establishing and enforcing structures and guidelines for authority and control (of data), thus concerning accountabilities and responsibilities: terms key to data governance. Approaching this from an enterprise perspective, as is often done in the present-day (Jonker et al., 2012), implies doing the aforementioned consistent with the overall organisational strategy and goals and doing this enterprise-wide instead of isolated or siloed (Henderson, 2017).

Considering the lack of a universally accepted notion of 'data governance' and the multifaceted characteristics of the discipline it seems appropriate to build on different constructs in the literature to establish what data governance means. The following definitions and characterisations of data governance can best be combined to get a comprehensive view of what is considered 'data governance' within this research:

-
- “Data Governance is the business practice that defines and manages strategies for people, processes, and technologies to ensure that valuable data assets are formally protected and managed throughout the organisation.” (Gregory, 2011, p. 235).
 - “Data governance refers to who holds the decision rights and is held accountable for an organization’s decision-making about its data assets.” (Khatri & Brown, 2010, p. 149).
 - “Data Governance specifies who in a company is allowed to make what decisions regarding the handling of data (rights), and what the tasks related to this decision-making are (duties) ... [Data Governance is] a companywide framework for assigning decision-related rights and duties in order to be able to adequately handle data as a company asset.” (Otto, 2011b, p. 47).

Moreover, the distinction between data management- and data governance practices can serve to further define and finalise the scope of data governance within this research. Building on the ‘DAMA wheel’ depicted in the DAMA-DMBOK, data management can be seen as the organisational capability concerned with *all* aspects of data and information, like ensuring value from data for consistent strategic decision-making, technical/operational matters concerning data storage, how to properly secure data and so on (Henderson, 2017). It can thus be seen as the organisational capability concerning data- and information practices at the highest level of abstraction. Data governance is at the centre of this, as depicted in the ‘DAMA wheel’ (Henderson, 2017). The data governance capability develops and enforces the supporting framework of control and authority for all aspects of data management practices. It can thus be said that while data management concerns the achievement of organisational goals and strategies related to data, data governance concerns ensuring that data is properly managed (Henderson, 2017).

3.3 Ownership and Data Ownership

Data ownership is among the most well-established concepts within the field of data governance. Ownership, as defined in the Merriam-Webster dictionary, is “the state, relation or fact of being an *owner*” (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-b), an ‘owner’ being “a person who owns something: one who has the legal or rightful title to something: one to whom property belongs” (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-a). While the concept of data ownership does not concern the legal ownership of something and should by no means be confused with copyright-related affairs, the idea remains similar and this definition serves well to illustrate that. Having a sense of ownership and a sense of being an owner induces a certain sense of responsibility and way of action-taking towards an artefact. This point has been shown in a variety of fields, like psychology, economics and information sciences (Wang et al., 1993; Van Alstyne et al., 1995; Pierce et al., 2001; Morewedge et al., 2009; Henderson, 2017; van Gils, 2020). The usage of the word *sense* of ownership and the *sense* of being an owner implies that the proverbial ‘owner’ need not necessarily be the legal or rightful owner to *feel* ownership over an artefact. The idea of data ownership hinges on this sense of ownership over a certain type of data, therefore inducing the owner to feel and act responsible for the data under management. The adopted meaning of data ownership during this research is in line with this stipulation of induced responsibility and accountability, thus acting accordingly and, hence, does not mean the Data Owner (discussed in section 3.5) is the legal owner of the data.

3.4 Enterprise- and siloed data management

The past decades have shown that many organisations increasingly approach data management from an organisation-wide (i.e. enterprise-wide) perspective rather than stand-alone per domain. In fact, the DAMA-DMBOK is stooled on this enterprise-view on data management practices (Henderson, 2017). Further considering the near unanimous thesis of data management and governance research that approaching these capabilities from an enterprise perspective is the new golden standard, it is safe to say the vast majority of organisations are or will be transitioning towards this perspective (Jonker et al., 2012; Alhassan et al., 2016; Henderson, 2017; Harrison et al., 2018; Schilling et al., 2020; van Gils, 2020; Aarnoutse, 2021). However, as many organisations are yet to transition or are still transitioning to this enterprise perspective of data management and data governance (Jonker et al., 2012), it is important to consider the fact that organisations will exhibit varying degrees of advancements. Differing characteristics belonging to enterprise- and ‘siloed’ data management, terms discussed below, can be established based on literature. Considering these differing characteristics ensures that organisations exhibiting varying degrees of advancements in their transitions towards enterprise data management have been considered.

Data management from an enterprise perspective involves an organisation-wide view of structuring information systems “in an effort to share information across business functions and hierarchical levels” (Harrison et al., 2018; Tableau, n.d.). On the opposite side lies ‘siloed’ data management. The usage of the term ‘siloed’ lends itself from the idea of data silos: idiosyncratic, compartmentalised and disparate information systems containing data that exhibits similar inconsistent characteristics when compared across domain boundaries (Harrison et al., 2018; Stedman, 2021). Table 3 contains characteristics of both data management ‘categories’.

Enterprise data management	Siloed data management
High interoperability and integration of datasets, databases and information systems.	Low/no interoperability and integration of datasets, databases and information systems, leading to a multitude of (duplicate) databases and information systems.
Data oftentimes available across domain boundaries on request through formalised processes and/or systems, such as a data market place or ‘data booth’ (<i>‘data loket’</i>). This degree of formalisation also implies that purposive attention has been given to authorisation rights and securing systems to prevent data leakages.	Often no formal process or system in place for data requests. Data is shared based on subjective demands with little/no considerations of authorisation rights and or security issues.
High level of data-consistency, both technical (e.g. consistent formatting) and semantical (e.g. through construction of business glossary or lexicon). The latter implies purposive attention has been given to consistent definitions and semantics across domains, for example through data-modelling.	Data often inconsistent, implying a multitude of different formatting styles and little/no consideration for varying constructs of definitions within the organisation.
High levels of collaboration and consultation between/across domain boundaries are present and are encouraged through formal working procedures and processes, examples of which are formalised networks, working groups and/or communities.	Little/no collaboration, both formally and/or informally, relying solely on subjective (in)actions by the agents involved in data-related organisational practices.

Table 3. Enterprise vs Siloed data management (Henderson, 2017; Harrison et al., 2018; Schilling et al., 2020; Aarnoutse, 2021; Stedman, 2021).

The characteristics of both data management categories can almost be seen as antonyms to one another, as should have become clear while reading. While the formulation in table 3 is rather black-and-white, organisations can exhibit varying extents to which enterprise and/or siloed data management aspects are present. Partially antedating the discussion in section 3.6, organisations exhibiting characteristics of siloed data management often exhibit a low level of data governance maturity, while organisations exhibiting enterprise data management characteristics have a higher data governance maturity. Since this list was potentially not exhaustive, other characteristics exhibiting similar oppositions can potentially be identified when considering varying states of transition towards enterprise data management.

3.5 Ownership models

The term ‘ownership model’ stems from van Gils (2020), who terms these models ‘ownership/stewardship models’. Due to the centrality of data ownership in these models, the author adopted the term ‘ownership model’. Ownership models are a type of model in the data governance structure that generally use the assignment of roles (van Gils, 2020). The general aim of such a model is to ensure usage, management and maintenance of data are coordinated in a formal manner, the latter resulting in fewer data issues. Different roles that are generally present in formalised ownership models and what their roles imply can be described as follows:

- **Data Owners.** Being the proverbial owner of certain data, in line with section 2.3, involves certain accountabilities for that data. This implies the Data Owner is ultimately accountable for a specific dataset, relating to a variety of aspects, such as ensuring data quality, accessibility, compliance, security, privacy, adherence to data governance policies and business value of the data (Henderson, 2017; Spacey, 2017; van Gils; Zagoudis, 2021). It is common for Data Owners to have (near) executive roles.
- **Data Stewards.** Data Stewards generally have practical hands-on responsibility for issues related to the aspects above. Data Stewards are often ‘delegated’ tasks by Data Owners in the sense that they are the ones responsible for the fulfilment of the aspects for which the Data Owner is accountable. This involves coordination and collaboration between Data Owners and employees fulfilling operational/technical roles. Following this, Data Stewards often have a mixed background in IT and business (Henderson, 2017; van Gils, 2020).
- **Data Users.** Data Users are generally agents wanting to use a certain type of data. Commonly, they negotiate with another role, often the Data Owner and often under the mediation of a Data Steward, about access to certain data, the definitions of that data and the requirements of that data (van Gils, 2020; Aarnoutse, 2021).

A depiction of an ownership model like the one described above, including the aforementioned general roles, can be seen in figure 4.

Figure 4. Example of an ownership model with the aforementioned roles (van Gils, 2020).

If formalised, this role-based model generally depicts lines connecting different roles to indicate the primary interaction between agents while fulfilling their roles (seen in figure 4). If formalised, roles, depending on the specific role, generally contain (at least some) of the aforementioned elements, like accountabilities, responsibilities and concrete activities, tasks or duties (Spacey, 2017; Henderson, 2017; van Gils, 2020; Zagoudis, 2021).

Researching literature exposes a range of varying descriptions for the same or similar concepts. Among different role names are Data Owners, Data Stewards, Data Custodians, Data Trustee, Data Users, Data Consumers, Data facilitators and any of the above combined with a title such as executive, chief, technical, business, coordinating and so on (Henderson, 2017; van Gils, 2020; Aarnoutse, 2021; Zagoudis, 2021). Furthermore, not all definitions or explanations of these roles mean the same. According to the DAMA DMBOK (Henderson, 2017), for example, ‘custodian’ and ‘trustee’ are often used synonymously to describe ‘stewards’. However, considering how Spacey (2017), van Gils (2020) and Zagoudis (2021) describe Data Owners, it seems to contain the element of ‘accountabilities’ that in the DAMA DMBOK (Henderson, 2017) are contained in stewardship roles. Similarly, Data Users and Data Consumers are often used synonymously though they are not necessarily the same (Aarnoutse, 2021). Considering Aarnoutse’s research, Data Consumers are said to simply utilise data in their work and produce data through their work without having any data management responsibilities, thus differing from Data Users as they are engaged in negotiating the properties of the data they are trying to access (Aarnoutse, 2021). The recentness of ownership model implementations in practice and the futility of the concept in scholarly work do no doubt contribute to this diversity in terminology and definitions. Moreover, linguistics are inherently different among organisations depending on the organisational culture, implying the same holds for defining such roles. It should be clear that this proliferation of terms, definitions and differing containments of roles in literature makes it much more complex for organisations to identify and adopt what fits their needs.

The aforementioned ownership model, the roles contained in the model and the plethora of function profiles, terminology and definitions associated with it are not where the complexity of addressing ownership models stops. Further adding to the complexity of ownership model implementations is the fact that many (smaller) organisations, being relatively immature in terms of their data governance practices, rely on informal and rather subjective ways in which activities, accountabilities and responsibilities are arranged. This might mean that someone (partially) acts as a Data Owner, Steward or User, but is not formally assigned or recognised as such. Besides the issues this might cause in the general conduct of their work, this further complicates the process of diagnosing the current ownership model state and identifying and adopting what fits the organisation's needs.

3.6 Establishing the theoretical basis for a new practical tool

As was mentioned before, hardly any scientifically validated practical tools for data governance practices exist (Merkus, 2015; Comuzzi & Patel, 2016) and, to the author's knowledge, no such tools exist to assist when designing and/or implementing ownership models. What follows in this section is a review of existing literature to assist in the construction of such a tool: the OMIT. Therefore, first, a review of existing practical data governance tools is put forward. Second, and building on this review, relevant dimensions are established to serve as input for the initial interviews. Combining these findings literature and interview findings, in turn, enables the construction of the OMIT during phase two of the research.

3.6.1 Existing practical data governance tools

Despite the general lack of scientifically validated tools in the field of data governance, a variety of practical data governance tools do exist. Among these tools are Data Governance Maturity Models, or DGMMs (Firican, n.d.; Merkus; 2015). Such maturity models serve as a "... technique to assess business processes or certain aspects of organisations, as it represents a path towards an increasingly organised and systematic way of doing business." (Proença & Borbinha, 2018, p. 1). While Merkus (2015), Comuzzi and Patel (2016) and Marchildon et al. (2018) provide and refine some of the first scientifically validated DGMMs, maturity models like these are generally based on best practices and developed by major IS/consulting firms preceded their efforts. Merkus (2015) seems to dismiss the utility of these best-practice models altogether as they: "... do not meet the requirements of scientifically sound modelling, such as verifiability or reproducibility." (Merkus, 2015, p. 18). While the author agrees with the essence of this statement, dismissing the utility of these models altogether while they are among the sole existing practical tools present in literature seems unwise and unnecessary. In fact, the author argues that including these tools in the development of new practical tools by building on their characteristics and subsequently scientifically validating the final tool at least partially solves the issues voiced by Merkus (2015).

A range of maturity models based on best practices are the data governance council maturity model developed by IBM (Adler, 2007), the maturity model developed by Stanford University's Data Governance Office (Firican, n.d.), the DataFlux maturity model (DataFlux, n.d.),

the Gartner governance maturity model (Newman & Logan, 2008) and Oracle's DGMM (Sun, 2011). These models all work similarly while differing in their construction and visualisation. Two general aspects can be identified within data governance maturity models (Comuzzi & Patel, 2016). First, a set of relevant organisational domains/dimensions related to data governance are listed to indicate the focal points for assessment, thus defining the scope of the assessment. Second, an assessment model is provided to enable organisational maturity assessment of the relevant dimensions along a certain measurement scale, often five maturity levels. This, in turn, should enable organisations to assess their current data governance maturity, enabling a more informed and target-oriented design and implementation of their overall data governance framework (Adler, 2007; Comuzzi & Patel, 2016; Marchildon et al., 2018).

Considering the works by Merkus (2015), Comuzzi and Patel (2016) and Marchildon et al., (2018), their developed DGMMs differ in the sense that they were constructed, validated and reported on scientifically, thereby taking into account reproducibility and verifiability. However, the construct and design of their maturity models are similar. Merkus (2015), based on an extensive literature review of existing governance frameworks instead of based on best practices, establishes data governance dimensions along which organisations should assess their maturity to gain a proper understanding of their current maturity state. The notion of defining crucial governance dimensions along which organisations can make an assessment is particularly useful for the current research, as will become clear in the following section.

Interestingly and rightfully noted by Marchildon et al. (2018): "... most of these approaches [i.e. DGMMs] are incomplete as they do not provide the necessary tools to help organizations accurately assess their own level of maturity in terms of data governance." (Marchildon et al., 2018, p. 158). While analysing both Merkus' DGMM and the best-practice DGMMs, it becomes clear that the relevant domains or dimensions to be assessed are propagated, while a concrete method or the concrete tools to conduct this assessment are missing. For example, Adler (2007) does highlight certain benchmarks through which organisations could assess the maturity of two dimensions but merely does so as an example. Similarly, Merkus substantiates the scientific construction and validation of his DGMM and provides an example of how the DGMM looks like after an organisational assessment (Merkus, 2015), but fails to accompany his model with concrete ways or examples of how this assessment was conducted and how maturity scores were established for certain dimensions. The author argues that the lack of such concrete examples or further tools to facilitate self-assessment by organisations defeats the purpose of said practical tools, rendering them less 'practical'. This insight led the author to incorporate such concreteness into the OMIT, as should become clear in chapter 5 of the research.

As mentioned, no practical tools were identified that assist organisations specifically in implementing or developing ownership models. However, a widely adopted practical tool that is often utilised to formalise and visualise the assignment of specific activities, responsibilities and accountabilities related to roles within an ownership model exists in the form of RACI- or RASCI-matrices. RA(S)CI stands for Responsible, Accountable, Supported, Consulted and Informed (Henderson, 2017). A mundane example of a RA(S)CI-matrix is shown in figure 5.

Activities	Functions										
	CEO	CFD	Business Executive	CIO	Business Process Owner	Head Operations	Chief Architect	Head Development	Head IT Administration	PMO	Compliance, Audit, Risk and Security
Link business goals to IT goals.	C	I	A/R	R	C						
Identify critical dependencies and current performance.	C	C	R	A/R	C	C	C	C	C		C
Build an IT strategic plan.	A	C	C	R	I	C	C	C	C	I	C
Build IT tactical plans.	C	I		A	C	C	C	C	C	R	I
Analyse programme portfolios and manage project and service portfolios.	C	I	I	A	R	R	C	R	C	C	I

A RACI chart identifies who is Responsible, Accountable, Consulted and/or Informed.

Figure 5. Example of a RACI-matrix (IT Governance Institute, 2005).

The figure shows activities on the y-axis, while the different roles are situated on the x-axis. The resulting matrix is then filled with the letters 'RA(S)CI' to indicate who is ultimately accountable (A) for an activity, who is responsible (R), who is supporting (S) the ones responsible, who needs to be consulted (C) before decisions are made and, finally, who needs to be informed (I) once an activity has been finalised or a decision has been made (IT Governance Institute, 2005; Weber et al., 2009; Henderson, 2017). Since formalised roles within an ownership model generally contain elements like responsibilities, activities and accountabilities and since RA(S)CI-matrices are designed to formalise (i.e. assign) and visualise exactly this, it should be clear why the model is particularly well-suited in formalising the containments of roles within an ownership model.

3.6.2 Relevant ownership model characteristics

In this section, relevant ownership model characteristics are identified based on existing literature. Table 4 gives an overview of these initial characteristics and the sources that indicated these characteristics to be of central importance to ownership models. The following discussion highlights how these characteristics emerged from the literature.

	Adler (2007)	Newman & Logan (2008)	Sun (2011)	Merkus (2015)	Henderson (2017)	Marchildon et al. (2018)	van Gils (2020)	Aarnoutse (2021)	DataFlux (n.d.)
Data quality	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
Risk mitigation	X		X						
Data as an asset	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Strategy formation									X
Organisational control	X	X	X		X	X			X
Data access and usage					X		X	X	
Data modelling and forming definitions					X		X	X	X
Managerial activities - role assignment			X		X		X		
Design activities - role creation			X				X		
Managerial/design activities - KPIs			X			X			
Defining ownership model scope							X		
Prerequisites - top-down support			X		X		X		
Prerequisites - Cultivating data culture					X		X		
Prerequisites - Holistic approach			X		X		X		

Table 4. Overview of existing sources that were used for relevant ownership model characteristics.

Merkus (2015), in line with van Gils (2020) and Henderson (2017), argues data ownership, used synonymously with data stewardship, is associated with the assignment of concrete responsibilities, accountabilities and activities. Specific tasks then relate to data quality considerations and ensuring data is managed as an asset (Merkus, 2015). Supporting this, Adler (2007) discusses 'stewardship', corresponding to the adopted meaning of 'ownership' in the current research, as a central category in the IBM data governance council maturity model, saying 'stewardship' concerns "... a quality control discipline designed to ensure custodial care of data for asset enhancement, risk mitigation, and organisational control." (Adler, 2007, p. 10). Marchildon et al. (2018) further support this claim, as they build on the same framework as Adler. Similarly, Newman and Logan (2008) consider 'Stewards' and stewardship, again synonyms to what we termed earlier as 'Owners' and ownership, to be associated with (formal) data-quality programs, associated responsibilities and enhancing information management as asset management, thus in line with the viewing data as central to creating business value. Considering the whitepaper by DataFlux (n.d.), further in line with the aforementioned theses, stewards are associated with implementing data management strategies and with enacting and maintaining enterprise-wide data definitions and cross-domain business rules relating to data integrity/quality. Further substantiating, Sun (2011), in Oracle's DGMM whitepaper, associates ownership and stewardship, or Data Owners and Data Stewards, with business engagement, thus in line with viewing data as a central business asset, and assigning clear responsibilities related to effective control and use of *data assets*.

Further characteristics, both related and unrelated to what has so far been mentioned, can be identified through van Gils' (2020) and Aarnoutse's (2021) research. They argue that in essence, ownership models serve as a formalised coordinating model to ensure proper management, maintenance and usage of data. While the former two aspects of this argument correspond to what has already been mentioned, thus in line with the claims by Adler (2007), Newman and Logan (2008), Sun (2011), Henderson (2017), Marchildon et al. (2018) and DataFlux (n.d.) that ownership models are about (data) quality and organisational control mechanisms (i.e. data management and maintenance), the latter aspect has yet to be discussed. The lacking presence of or attention to Data Users in many ownership models, according to Aarnoutse (2021), potentially undermines the crucial part Users play in negotiating data usage. Users are said to negotiate with Owners or Stewards about access to data, the definitions of that data and the requirements of that data (van Gils, 2020; Aarnoutse, 2021). In more formalised settings this is sometimes done through drafting Data Sharing Agreements (DSAs). A DSA contains agreements between Data Users and Data Owners about the intended use of the data, restrictions to the data's usage, expected quality or service levels and other potentially relevant agreements (Henderson, 2017; Aarnoutse, 2021). In this way, Data Users are not merely consuming data, as is the case for Data Consumers (Aarnoutse, 2021), but are actively involved in data management activities. Closely related are processes through which (requests for) access to data are handled and platforms facilitating this, such as a data marketplace (Aarnoutse, 2021). Formalising these

processes, potentially by actors within the ownership model itself, further facilitates the interactions within an ownership model.

Briefly mentioned before, defining terms thus creating definitions paramount to understanding what certain data is actually about instead of relying on assumptions, is another characteristic linked to actors within ownership models (Henderson, 2017; van Gils, 2020; Aarnoutse, 2021; DataFlux, n.d.). This includes modelling activities to create a conceptual domain model, often called data modelling, domain modelling or business domain modelling. While it is often propagated that Owners or Stewards (used synonymously) act as the central agents in domain modelling activities (Henderson, 2017; DataFlux, n.d.), more modern approaches consider the interplay between Owners and Users (van Gils, 2020) or even consider entirely separate roles concerned with modelling tasks (Aarnoutse, 2021). Regardless of the specific organisational implementation, domain modelling or, less formal, formalising crucial terms through definitions can be seen as another characteristic closely linked to ownership models.

Ownership model characteristics relating to managerial or design issues can also be identified, such as who should get a certain role, whether official positions should be created and defining metrics to measure the performance of agents. Turning to this first managerial aspect, Van Gils (2020) and Sun (2011), in line with Henderson (2017), argue that fulfillers of ownership model roles are best found instead of being made or assigned. This implies that merely assigning roles or tasks in a top-down manner is not helpful. Rather, inviting empowered agents who naturally feel ownership or stewardship in a bottom-up manner to fulfil these roles is said to work better. Therefore, it is argued that the identification process of roles is paramount and should be given ample time (Sun, 2011; van Gils, 2020). Considering the second managerial aspect, Sun (2011) argues that official functions or positions need not necessarily be created for Stewards or Owners, as long as their roles are included in their formal job description and, hence, time is allocated for the fulfilment of said roles. Furthermore, Sun (2011) considers stewardship coverage across domain boundaries within the organisation, therefore incorporating the entire enterprise in stewardship practices, as a key metric to data governance activities. However, specific KPIs or metrics to measure performance related to ownership model responsibilities and tasks are not identified in existing literature.

Another ownership model characteristic that has yet to be discussed concerns the categorisation or defining of the scope of data for which agents are to be accountable/responsible (van Gils, 2020). Van Gils, based on a presentation by Polsky (2013) highlights certain scopes, both theoretical and identified in practice, such as categorising data 1) according to subject area (e.g. customer data, product data, financial data), 2) according to business function (e.g. Sales, Marketing, HR), 3) according to applications or systems, 4) according to business processes or 5) according to specific projects. While a mindful reader might notice that Owners within the latter three ownership model categorisations could perhaps better be called System Owners, Process Owners or Project Owners, it should mainly become clear that the choice an organisation makes, be it conscious or unconscious, has implications for the way Ownership and Stewardship of data are fulfilled. It is therefore an important characterisation of ownership models to consider.

Finalising this section, certain characterisations can be identified that seem to be framed as prerequisites to the relative success of ownership models. First, the agents fulfilling the roles contained in an ownership model and the data governance activities they fulfil need executive endorsement from the organisations. Thus, however obvious it may seem, top-down support is crucial as well (Henderson, 2017; van Gils, 2020). Second, according to Henderson (2017), besides top-down support, it is important that the entire organisation sees the added value of proper data management and acts accordingly in their daily conduct. Therefore, there is a large cultural component underlying the success of data management and governance and, accordingly, the exploitation of data within organisations. Third, multiple authors propagate the necessity to approach ownership models holistically instead of isolated (Sun, 2011; Henderson, 2017; van Gils, 2020). Since affiliated ownership model practices are wide and intertwined with more general data management and data governance practices, it is important to note that merely addressing and implementing an ownership model will not get the organisation forward. Rather, by viewing an ownership model as a mere part of a larger whole (i.e. holistically), meaning the overall enterprise data management and/or data governance framework, it is ensured that the necessary complementary policies, processes and practices are in place that can together lead to successful data governance.

4. Phase one: Interview findings

Relevant ownership model characteristics extracted from existing literature were presented in section 3.6.2. These initial characteristics, based on secondary data, firstly served as input for the interviews during phase one that were conducted with experts from the five organisations discussed in section 2.1. The initial interviews both led to the corroboration of relevant ownership model characteristics presented in section 3.6.2 as well as to the emergence of further relevant ownership model characteristics. Combining the findings in section 3.6.2 and the phase one interview findings, concluding phase one of the research, led to a conceptual model that formed the basis for OMIT development in chapter 5.

This chapter is structured as follows. First, the conceptual model is presented by illustrating its construction based on the interview findings, thus formulating an answer to SQ5. Second, differences in organisations' ownership model maturity are discussed, as to answer SQ3. Finally, a discussion of the challenges that organisations generally encounter related to ownership models is provided, as to answer SQ2. By finalising the answers to SQ2, SQ3 and SQ5 in combination with the partial answers already provided during the literature review, questions SQ1 to SQ5 are conclusively answered and, hence, provide an answer to main RQ1.

4.1 Conceptual model: ownership model characteristics

A conceptual model containing central ownership model characteristics and topics is presented in figure 6.

Figure 6. Conceptual model of central ownership model characteristics.

The conceptual model's elements are presented and explained by illustrating how they emerged from the phase one interviews and how this emergence can be linked to the literature findings in 3.6.2. Where appropriate, quotations responses are provided to illustrate how elements emerged from the data. Provided quotations are linked to participants based on priorly shown table 1. Both the original Dutch quotation is presented in order to preserve the intended meaning of participants, as well as the English translation for non-Dutch readers. The latter readers should bear in mind that the intended meanings may be partially lost in translation.

Accountabilities, Responsibilities, Activities

The central thesis of an ownership model is the distribution and construction of data-related accountabilities, responsibilities and activities, based on certain roles, in a formalised manner. This was already shown in the literature findings in section 3.6.2 and was supported en masse when analysing the interviews. Interviewees talked about how Data Owners were often ultimately *accountable* when data-related problems occurred and how other roles were *responsible* for more operational data-related *activities*. To indicate the centrality of this ownership model aspect it was placed at the top of the conceptual model, as to indicate that all of the subsequent conceptual model's elements are concerned with data-related accountabilities, responsibilities or activities.

Central Topics

A set of six central topics could be extracted based on the interview findings, combined with the literature findings in section 3.6.2. These topics were Data Quality & Integrity, Privacy & Security, Risk & Compliance, Organisational Control, Data access & Usage and People & Culture. The emergence of these topics is illustrated below.

Data Quality & Integrity. Questioned about the different accountabilities, responsibilities and tasks of Data Owners, one argued:

“That is of course signalling data quality issues, so to speak. That is of course one [topic]. Then also the maintenance and management of the data, so ensuring that data is and remains up to date. Above all reliable, valid and consistent. I think those are the most important things”. [Participant 3]

“Dat is enerzijds natuurlijk signaleren van data kwaliteitsissues, om het zo maar te zeggen. Dat is natuurlijk een [onderwerp]. Dan ook het onderhoud en beheer van de data, dus zorgen dat data ook actueel is en blijft. Vooral betrouwbaar, valide en consistent. Dat zijn denk ik wel de belangrijkste dingen...”. [Participant 3]

This quotation summarises that data quality and integrity-related accountabilities, responsibilities and tasks were prominently present in the interview findings. Activities ranged from actualising data, classifying data, creating data consistency, in a both technical and semantical sense, ensuring interoperability across systems and so on. It should be clear that the topical relevance of data quality and integrity is in line with the literature review discussed before.

Privacy & Security. Substantiated by a total of twenty-five separate mentions and no organisation leaving out this topic, it seems to be clear that privacy and security-related aspects are relevant for ownership models. Aspects ranged from ensuring proper and actualised authorisations, preventing data breaches, providing secure systems for data access and sharing and so on. Exemplary of the centrality of this topic was that while 4 out of 5 organisations were yet to introduce formal governance roles, all organisations already had a formal privacy officer or privacy champion. None of the reviewed literature considered privacy and security to be of central relevance to ownership models in specific. However, nearly all literature considered this topic to be of relevance to the organisational data governance framework. Since the ownership model is part of this data governance framework, it can be said that the emergence of this topic from the primary data as relevant to ownership models is at least partially in line with the literature findings.

Risk & Compliance. In many aspects closely linked to privacy and security-related tasks, risk and compliance was a topic that emerged from the primary data. Risk management within ownership models seemed to be mostly related to identifying security risks, mostly aiming to prevent data breaches and confidentiality breaches. Compliance seemed to be especially, though not exclusively, pressing in the highly regulated areas in which the municipality and governance agency found itself. Participants highlighted the massive importance of GDPR compliance, public law and compliance with other laws more specific to particular fields (not mentioned as to not breach confidentiality). Indicating the relevance of this topic, one organisation built its entire data management principles on GDPR compliance. This was the first time the organisation had constructed these principles, indicating how pressing GDPR compliance was for the organisations once this directive was enacted. Furthermore, one interviewee even argued compliance with laws and regulations to be one of the main drivers for implementing data ownership, saying:

“... you have the Dutch Open Government Act, right, and it also prescribes which data must be made available. Yes, and they [i.e. Data Owners] just have to work because if it is not on it [i.e. data is not openly available] then you are simply negligent and that is of course not allowed.”
[Participant 1]

“... je hebt de wet open overheid hè, en die heeft ook voorgeschreven welke data opengesteld moet worden. Ja, en die [i.e. Data Owners] móeten gewoon aan de bak want als het er niet op staat [i.e. als data niet openbaar beschikbaar is] dan ben je gewoon nalatig en dat mag natuurlijk niet.”
[Participant 1]

Similar to the previous topic, none of the reviewed literature mentioned risk and compliance as a central topic specifically for ownership models. However, risk and compliance was mentioned as a central topic to data governance frameworks in general, implying that the emergence of this topic from the primary data as relevant to ownership models is, again, at least partially in line with literature findings.

Data access & Usage. Data access and usage was found to be a relevant ownership model topic based on interview findings. This topic concerns ensuring and maintaining the accessibility of data for internal usage. This involved processes, both formal and informal, of requesting and subsequently accessing data, oftentimes through designated systems and according to established policies in line with the aforementioned two topics (i.e. privacy & security and risk & compliance). Participants also discussed how Users and Owners, oftentimes mediated by another agent such as a Steward, are involved in the process of negotiating data access and how this includes the establishment of definitions of the required data, data quality requirements, formal purposes for which data can be used, purposes for which data may not be used and so on. Data Sharing Agreements (DSA) were deployed in organisations where processes surrounding data access and usage were more mature/formalised. While only few sources specifically discussed the role of users in arranging and negotiating data access & usage, many sources did signify data access and usage as a relevant topic to ownership models. Hence, the interview findings were mostly consistent with the literature findings.

Organisational Control. Constructing ownership models can be seen as contributing to the overall organisational control mechanisms, as the data activities and corresponding accountabilities and responsibilities are structured and steered in a way as to align with the organisations' goals. Participants explained the reasons to adopt a certain management style or to allocate roles to employees as conscious means to steer the organisational data activities towards an intended outcome. Talking about one of the responsibilities of a particular role, one participant said:

"... the 'originator' actually has to monitor that what we want as an [organisation] is being achieved ... And he must also ensure that financial resources are made available to realise that where necessary." [Participant 5]

"... die opdrachtgever die moet eigenlijk bewaken dat wat we als [organisatie] willen ook bereikt wordt ... En die moet ook zorgen dat er dan financiële middelen beschikbaar worden gesteld om dat dan ook te realiseren waar dat dan nodig is." [Participant 5]

This quotation indicates that constructing an ownership model, meaning the roles contained in the model and the specific accountabilities, responsibilities and activities they ought to perform, is a means to ensure data activities are in line with organisational goals. This highlights why ownership models can be seen as organisational control mechanisms, thus proving organisational control is a relevant topic for ownership models. The latter argument is also in line with the literature findings.

People & Culture. A final central topic within ownership models that could be identified based on the interview findings are the people within and the culture of the organisation. Interviewing participants made clear that the organisational culture determines the style in which ownership models are developed, whether they even are developed and, if they are, the degree of formality

of roles and functions within the ownership model, how roles are allocated, what terminology is used and so on. The latter was already argued before to complexify the organisation's task of identifying appropriate ownership models. While this argument has not been grounded through the interviews, the interview findings did support the plethora of terms for functions and roles. For example, one participant argued the organisation consciously refrained from the usage of the term 'ownership', while the containments and characteristics of the role in question were clearly in line with a Data Owner based on literature. The following quotation should illustrate this:

"... ownership does something [to a person] because if I take your headphones away you will get angry", pointing to the headphones the author was wearing, continuing to say: "So it really is 'commissionership' and with that, we avoid the word 'owner' on all sides because before you know it the director is going to say 'Yes that's mine, all mine, mine, mine', no it's not yours, it's from [organisation]." [Participant 5]

"... eigenaarschap dat doet namelijk iets, want als ik nou jouw koptelefoon af pak dan word jij boos." ... "Dus het is echt een opdrachtgeverschap en daarmee vermijden we aan alle kanten het woord 'eigenaar', want voor je het weet gaat de directeur zeggen 'Ja dat is mijn, allemaal van mij, mij, mij', nee het is niet van jou, het is van [organisatie]." [Participant 5]

Furthermore, management styles differed substantially per organisation, indicating how the people and, correspondingly, the culture determine how all ownership model-related activities are conducted. This indicates why this topic is of central relevance to ownership models.

Different categories of ownership model activities

Different central topics were just discussed to which accountabilities, responsibilities and activities within ownership models relate. Further emerging from the data, many of the central activities surrounding ownership models could be divided into categories. These categories, discussed hereafter, are activities on an executive level, managerial level and design activities related to ownership models.

Central activities and responsibilities that emerged from combining the primary and secondary data could be further ascribed to these three categories and, hence, are listed below each of the categories they belonged to.

Executive level:

- *Resources.* Interestingly, hardly any of the reviewed literature seemed to address the elephant in the room and argued that resources and resource allocation were paramount to ownership models or governance practices. Perhaps this follows from the obviousness of this statement, but it is important to consider nonetheless: money needs to be available in order to have time and space to conduct governance activities. (In)available time and money often resulted from executive-level decisions, but also in collaboration with employees lower in the organisational hierarchy, as resource allocation to specific functions or projects was usually carried out at a managerial level. An example that indicated the centrality of this executive responsibility was

the unavailability of money for the creation of new functions or for freeing up time in existing functions while the quartermaster clearly deemed this as essential for improving data governance. Another example was a participant explaining the difficulties of skewed availability of resources and designing an enterprise-wide budget for governance practices encompassing multiple domains within the organisations as a solution, further indicating the centrality of this responsibility:

“[for example] data ownership of sources that are used across different value chains. ... It could be that the ‘Sampling’-domain says “I think there should be a lot more data stewardship.” And then the ‘Enforcing’-domain says “All well and good, but I don’t have money for that.”. That is why I say within the various bodies that decide on this that we have a coordinative data council. ... That data council must also have money to say “Yes, this is something [organisation]-wide. Ten per cent of our funds are available for that.”. So then the ‘Sampling’-domain can say: ‘I think that’s important’ and can then claim from that budget and then we can at least execute it.” [Participant 4]

“ [bijvoorbeeld] gegevenseigenaarschap van bronnen die over verschillende waardeketens gebruikt worden. ... Dan kan het wezen dat bij ons het domein ‘Keuren’ zegt van “Ik vind dat er veel meer data stewardship op moet worden gepleegd”. En dan zegt ‘Handhaven’ van “Dat is goed joh maar ik heb daar geen geld voor.”. Vandaar dat ik ook binnen die verschillende gremia die daarover besluiten zeg dat we een datacoördinatie beraad hebben. ... Dat datacoördinatie beraad moet ook geld hebben om te zeggen “Ja, nu hebben we iets [organisatie]-breeds. Tien procent van onze fondsen is daar beschikbaar voor.”. Dus dan kan een divisie ‘Keuren’ zeggen van “Ik vind dat dat belangrijk is”. Die kan uit dat potje claimen en dan kunnen we het in elk geval uitvoeren.” [Participant 4]

- *Strategy, Vision & Policies.* Present in the interview findings were data strategy formation, the creation of a future vision or roadmap for data practices and the construction of data policies, all done at or in collaboration with the executive level of the organisation. Examples were the quartermaster formalising a data strategy in line with the organisational strategy and proposing this to the board of directors for approval, the enterprise architect formulating ‘a data foundation’ (*‘data fundament’*) as “rudimentary strategic data policies and principles” to be used for guidance in data practices and the strategic choice to adopt a data mash framework. While the naming of this central activity or responsibility was defined by the author, the development and enactment of policies and strategic decision-making is in line with findings from the literature.
- *Data as an asset.* This central responsibility concerns the alignment of data activities with business goals and values, thus viewing data as an organisational asset and exploiting it as such. The attentive reader must have noticed the close link to the previous central activities in that it is the executive’s responsibility, collaborating with lower-level organisational members, to develop and execute strategies, vision and policies in line with this ‘data as an asset’-perspective. This central responsibility emerged from the data as multiple participants continuously highlighted that policies or processes were designed in ways that ensure the

organisational goals are met and data activities are carried out in accordance with the data strategy, vision and/or roadmap. Furthermore, this central responsibility is at least partially in line with literature findings as it was mentioned as central to data governance in general.

Managerial level:

- *Managing People.* One of the central responsibilities and activities that emerged from the data was the necessity for consciously managing people within the organisations' data governance practices. This did not necessarily say something about the nature of the management style, as both top-down versus bottom-up and prescriptive versus participative management styles were identified. What was common, however, was the conscious positioning and propagation of a certain management style on the managerial level. None of the reviewed secondary sources of data indicated specifically to managing people as a central responsibility within ownership model/data governance practices. However, as will become clear in the next central activity, certain sources did propagate a participative or bottom-up management style in which the management of people was the focal point for success. Therefore, the central managerial responsibility of managing people, apart from the nature of the management style, is in line with the literature findings.

- *Allocation of Roles & Functions.* The allocation of ownership model roles and/or functions within an ownership model emerged from the primary data as a further central managerial activity and responsibility, in line with literature findings. Closely linked with the management style that an organisation propagated, fulfillers of roles or functions were mostly searched bottom-up, but were also assigned top-down in some cases. Interestingly, it seemed that the organisation with the highest ownership model and data governance maturity propagated a more top-down and formalised way of role/function allocation than other organisations, while literature suggested that this is not necessarily a successful approach. The following quotation illustrates how allocating roles and/or functions within an ownership model emerged as a central managerial activity and how this was consciously done in a bottom-up/participative manner, further in line with literature findings:

"So I am now trying to gain momentum through a coalition of the willing, also to be able to explore that the approach we choose is the right approach and that the conversations we have with each other become the conversations that we need to have with each other, about [data] use and accountability for the use of data. So I'm trying to annotate that now. Well, that works. Now you also see that the fear of missing out is starting to play a role in certain developments, so "I actually want that too. What is it exactly? He is working on it and my colleague is already doing it and everyone is praising it and I want to participate too!". Well, I hope that at the end of the road ... I have found [Data] Owners for fifty per cent of the data domains of the [organisation] who also *feel* they are [Data] Owners." [Participant 4]

"Dus ik probeer nu vanuit een coalition of the willing momentum te krijgen, ook om te kunnen verkennen of de aanpak die we daarbij kiezen de goede aanpak is, en dat de gesprekken die we met

mekaar voeren de gesprekken worden die we met mekaar moeten voeren, over [data] gebruik en verantwoording afleggen over het gebruik van gegevens. Dus dat probeer ik nu te annoteren. Nou dat werkt. Nu zie je ook dat bij bepaalde ontwikkelingen de fear of missing out begint te spelen, dus "Ik wil dat eigenlijk ook. Wat is het nou precies? Hij is er mee bezig en mijn collega doet het al en iedereen is er lovend over en ik wil ook meedoen!". Nou, ik hoop dat ik aan het eind van de rit ... voor vijftig procent van de gegevensdomeinen van de [organisatie] eigenaren heb gevonden die zich [data] eigenaar voelen." [Participant 4]

- *Measuring Performance.* This central activity should be interpreted broadly as it includes both the performance of people, systems and data(sets). Measuring performance emerged almost entirely from the primary data as only one secondary source indicated that this is a potentially relevant ownership model-related aspect. Measuring the performance of people ranged from rather subjective and informal methods to more formal and objective methods. Examples of subjective and informal methods were measuring performance as the rough amount of attention Data Owners had given to a dataset based on the number of classified datasets or whether formal DSA's were established in most data sharing cases. Examples of objective and more formal methods, much like KPIs, were a measure of disturbances/availability of a certain system or source and a measure of data quality issues or user experiences of a certain system or dataset. The more objective measures for performance were exclusively concerned with systems or datasets. As the Data Owners were ultimately accountable and other roles were in some way or shape responsible for the performance of a system or datasets, managers used these measures as a measure for the performance of people as well.

Ownership model design:

- *Designing Model-scope.* Designing the ownership model started with the scope of the data that is managed and governed by agents within the model. The formulation of this central activity might sound as if organisations made a conscious decision for a certain scope, while it often resulted from mere practical considerations or emerged from non-data-related organisational designs. Adopted scopes ranged from business functions (e.g. HR, finance, marketing) to business processes (e.g. 'Sampling', 'Enforcing') and subject areas (e.g. 'public domain', 'learning environments'). The adopted scope dictated the number of Data Owners and, accordingly, other roles that were deemed necessary within the ownership model. This also indicates why a certain scope was often adopted out of practical considerations instead of freely chosen, as one participant mentioned: "We have thirteen sectors and therefore also thirteen sector directors [Data Owners], well for me thirteen people can still be managed ..." implying that the manageability was at the core for adopting this scope.
- *Designing Roles & Functions.* Central to ownership model design activities is the designing of roles and functions within the ownership model. All organisations seemed to agree that formal roles are necessary for the development of an ownership model, in line with the literature

findings. Formal functions, however, were not necessarily deemed necessary and, hence, were not always present for all roles. While 'Data Steward' was often both the formal function and formal ownership model role, Data Owners were often fulfilling their role as an extra task besides their formal function as director (for example). Ignoring the plethora of terminology used to describe roles and functions which was present, organisations seemed to roughly agree on having Data Owners, Data Stewards, Data Users and other miscellaneous roles supporting overall ownership model practices, like data architects, data product owners or data scientists.

- *Designing Role-containments.* Designing and formalising the specific accountabilities, responsibilities and activities that are expected from the different ownership model roles is a further central ownership model design activity. The degree of formalisation of role containments differed widely per organisation, but all participants seemed to agree that formalisation of role containments should be strived for. Specific containments related to all of the central topics in the conceptual model that were already discussed, like data quality and integrity-related tasks, ensuring security and privacy standards, ensuring compliance with regulation, managing and negotiating data access and usage and so on. While hardly any roles so far contained formal KPIs or measures due to ownership model maturity, all participants seemed to agree that performance measures should be part of ownership model role containments. The usage of RA(S)CI matrices, while not mentioned specifically by any participant, can assist with this central design activity.
- *Designing Model-processes.* The last ownership model design-related activity concerns the establishment of formal processes within the ownership model. Again, these formal processes are related to all of the aforementioned central topics in the central model. Examples were a formal process for requesting data access, formal processes according to a checklist for data quality implementations and formal processes for data transmission to ensure data security and enhance risk mitigation. It should be clear that the designing of formal processes is closely linked to the designing of role containments, as role containments, for example, stipulate a person's tasks within or responsibilities for a certain process.

Prerequisites

Finally, essential concepts for the success of ownership model implementations emerged from the primary data and were mostly in line with findings in the literature. These essential concepts were identified and are presented as prerequisites that need to be present or adhered to for a greater chance of success of ownership model practices and the overall ownership model implementation. These central concepts and their emergence are discussed below.

Cultivating a Data Culture. This first prerequisite concerns the need for cultivating a data culture, meaning the entire organisation from executive to operational employees understands the importance of data management and is aware of the potential when data is managed as such.

There was an emphatic presence of this first prerequisite in both interview findings and literature findings, the former indicated by the assignment of a related open code in over fifty instances. Participants understood the necessity for cultivating a data culture and consciously acted as such. Examples were given where participants tried to induce awareness of how data quality issues may lead to misinterpretations of data and disinformation at all levels of the organisation. Considering the aforementioned quote of one participant, saying that through seeking coalitions of the willing they aimed to create momentum and induce the fear of missing out on successful data governance practices, further exemplifies a conscious tactic to cultivate a data culture. Perfectly illustrating this consciousness and according action taking was one participant saying that:

“We are really organising community building. And we are really searching with our data program 'how can we make working data fun?'. To do so we also hired a communication agency to tell data stories in a glossy, to really let the people who work with data shine ...” [Participant 1]

“We zijn echt die community-vorming aan het organiseren. En we zijn echt aan het zoeken met ons data programma van 'hoe kunnen we werkende data leuk maken?'. Daarvoor hebben we ook een communicatiebureau in de arm genomen om echt in een glossy data verhalen te laten vertellen, om echt de mensen die met data werken te laten shinen...” [Participant 1]

As section 4.3 on organisational challenges will show, one of the organisational challenges related to ownership models followed directly from difficulties surrounding this first prerequisite.

Top-down support. While this second prerequisite was initially drawn from the literature, interview findings seemed to confirm its importance for successful governance practices. If there is no executive or top-down support for governance practices or agents within the ownership model, ownership models and governance practices will be neglected, resources will not be made available and, hence, the chance of the ownership model's failure will increase immensely. As one participant illustrated, discussing one of his priorities:

“ ... that is in any case what I am mainly concerned about, to make it clear to [executive] management in any case: “Yes guys, what you want is all well and good, but if you do not want to invest in this [data governance], keep dreaming, but then it [fulfilling organisational goals] is just not going to work.” [Participant 2]

“.. dat is in ieder geval waar ik mij vooral druk om maak, om in ieder geval bij het [executive] management duidelijk te maken van: “ja jongens, allemaal leuk en aardig wat jullie willen, maar als je hier [data governance] niet op wilt investeren, blijven dromen, maar dan gaat het [gestelde organisatiedoelen behalen] gewoon niet werken.” [Participant 2]

Holistic approach. The mindful reader will have noticed how interrelated all of the aforementioned elements within the conceptual model are. For example, top-down support goes hand-in-hand with the cultivation of a data culture, getting available resources with top-down

support, seeing and using data as an asset with a cultivated data culture, managing people with cultivating a data culture and so on. This illustrates the interconnectedness of all elements in the conceptual model and, hence, why it is important to fully grasp and embrace all conceptual model's elements as holistic instead of isolated.

Extending this argument, adopting a holistic approach towards the established ownership model elements and overall data governance practices can furthermore be seen as paramount to ownership model success. The latter is mostly supported by literature findings while not directly supported by interview findings. It should however be clear that viewing ownership models as part of a larger whole, the overall data governance framework, and that grasping the interconnectedness of ownership model elements increases the chance of successful ownership model practices. Therefore, adopting a holistic approach is argued to be a final prerequisite for ownership model implementations.

4.2 Ownership model maturity differences

Interview findings further served to establish differences in organisational ownership model maturity across participating organisations. The first part of the central thesis that emerged from the primary data was that ownership model maturities differ extensively across organisations and that especially relatively small organisations, with fewer than 5000 employees, seem to generally have a low ownership model maturity. The smallest four out of five organisations were all either in the process of creating or (partially) implementing topics from an established roadmap for data governance practices. Out of these four organisations, three highlighted that ownership models were still to be addressed on this roadmap while they did have some idea of where they wanted to go, indicated by one participant as:

“Well, in particular, the fact that we need data ownership [has been formalised] ... it has not been worked out very explicitly what that means. It has been included as an item in our roadmap, we have to do something with it ...” [Participant 2]

“Nou met name dat we data eigenaarschap nodig hebben [is geformaliseerd] ... er is nog niet heel expliciet uitgewerkt wat dat dan is. Het is als item opgenomen binnen onze roadmap, we moeten daar iets mee...” [Participant 2]

Only in the largest organisation were ownership model roles and functions made formal and implemented. In the four smallest organisations, ownership model roles were at best implemented fragmentedly, meaning for example that Data Owners were assigned but Data Stewards or Data Users were not or vice versa. Three out of four of the smallest organisations were ownership model roles neither made formal nor incorporated in formal task descriptions. In line with this, data quality, expressed by participants in terms of actualisation, classification, technical and semantical consistency and integration and interoperability of datasets and systems, was generally lower in organisations with a lower ownership model maturity. While the maturity of cross-domain collaboration, formalisation of data-related processes and formalisation of the process or system for data-access varied among organisations, the central tenet remained

that the smaller organisations generally had lower maturities on these ownership model aspects as well. Illustrating the overall tenet of ownership model maturity within the majority of the organisations:

“... we have so many data-level things not in order so that you just have to conclude... We like to talk about baselines and maturity levels, but that is just not well.” [Participant 2]

“... we hebben zó veel dingen op data-niveau nog niet op orde dat je gewoon moet constateren... We praten graag over baselines en volwassenheidsniveau, maar dat is gewoon niet best.” [Participant 2]

The second part of the central thesis that emerged from the interviews was that organisations did not only differ compared to each other but also the ownership model elements within individual organisations differed widely, thereby extending the previous argument. Within one organisation, there was an extensive formal process and a dedicated system for both data access and information product management, while the same organisation still had no formal ownership model roles implemented and even informal data ownership was still fragmented at the very best. Similarly, the largest organisation with the highest ownership model maturity had formalised and implemented ownership model roles and working processes within the ownership model but argued that the organisational data awareness was rather low even for the ownership model participants. Furthermore, indicating the far-reaching extent to which ownership model elements differed within individual organisations, one organisation had designed ownership model roles and was in the process of informally assigning roles but did not have any design, neither formal nor informal, of how these roles were to interact with each other within the model. Illustrating this, the participant from this organisation said:

“... that is part of the problem I think, these are named [i.e. formalised] roles but we have not organised an organisation or process around this so that they are also connected that might happen as an agenda item now and then, but there is no structured approach right now and... no, not really no.” [Participant 2]

“... dat is een deel van het probleem denk ik, dit zijn benoemde [geformaliseerde] rollen maar we hebben geen organisatie of proces daarom georganiseerd dat die ook met mekaar in verbinding zijn ... dat gebeurt nu misschien als een agendapunt af en toe, maar er is nu geen gestructureerde aanpak en ... nee, eigenlijk niet nee.” [Participant 2]

It should be clear that the large variance in the maturity of individual ownership model elements within individual organisations is a counterexample of approaching ownership models holistically; a point argued to be a prerequisite for successful ownership model implementations.

Finalising the core message extracted from the primary data, all organisations were transitioning towards data governance and, accordingly, ownership model implementations from an enterprise perspective. Siloed data management was present in all organisations while differing vastly in the extent to which this was the case, the latter depending on the ownership model maturity of the organisation. Nevertheless, even for organisations with a lesser maturity,

the contents of formulated data visions and roadmaps indicated a transition to data governance practices and, hence, ownership model practices from an enterprise perspective.

Summarising, and generalising from the research context, there are many organisations with a low ownership model maturity, a high variance in the maturity of ownership model elements within individual organisations and there are many organisations currently in an ongoing transition towards an enterprise perspective of ownership model practices. This implies that the OMIT should account for these large differences in ownership model maturity and should account for the fact that many organisations will be in the initial stages of ownership model development and implementation. Moreover, these findings strengthen the practical relevance of the OMIT considerably as many organisations will benefit from the development of an OMIT that accounts for low ownership model maturity.

4.3 Organisational challenges

Certain organisational challenges were identified related to relevant ownership model characteristics, presented in the conceptual model in section 4.1. First and most emphatically present, several organisations argued that there is a general lacking understanding of data as a construct, how data works, what working with data requires and what organisational potential can be unlocked when having proper data management/governance. Several quotes indicate that this immaturity of ‘data-thinking’ is present in all levels of the organisations, in line with the argument that the cultivation of a data culture is a prerequisite for ownership model success:

“The IT people think it [i.e. data] is something for the specialist department, and the specialist department thinks it is mainly an IT thing because you put in a system.” [Participant 1]

“De IT’ers vinden dat het iets van de vakafdeling is, en de vak-afdeling vindt dat het vooral iets van IT is want je zet het in een systeem neer.” [Participant 1]

“In HR we discovered that we have fifty interfaces to all kinds of different systems, while in fact we should be able to solve that with one or two data products. ... The advantage is that you also build much less ... But it is often difficult for people to understand.” [Participant 5]

“Bij HR hebben we ontdekt dat we vijftig interfaces hebben naar allerlei verschillende systemen, terwijl we dat in feite op moeten kunnen lossen met één á twee dataproducten. ... Het voordeel is je bouwt ook veel minder ... Maar het is wel moeilijk te begrijpen vaak voor mensen.” [Participant 5]

“Data remains something that is vague, in perception. ... Truly seeing data as an asset and using it as such is extremely difficult.” [Participant 3]

“Data blijft in de perceptie iets vaags. ... Data écht als een asset zien en ook zo gebruiken, dat is ontzettend moeilijk.” [Participant 3]

Extending this, and directly connected to a lacking data culture or organisational data awareness, top-down support seemed to be lacking, in some cases, for data governance practices. Following

this lack of top-down endorsement, organisations argued that available resources were scarce for data governance activities and data governance activities had to compete with other matters that were often deemed more pressing. Illustrating this, participants said:

“So what essentially results from the change that working with data entails is a lot of new [necessary] functions, and there is simply no money for new functions. So there is simply no money being made available.” [Participant 1]

“Wat dus in wezen de verandering die het werken met data met zich meebrengt tot gevolg heeft is heel veel nieuwe [benodigde] functies, en voor nieuwe functies is gewoon geen geld. Dus er wordt gewoon geen geld beschikbaar gemaakt.” [Participant 1]

“... our Information-Provision-policy neatly states that data is not a cost-item but a value creator, a wonderful statement, but if you do not want to spend a euro on it then...” [Participant 2]

“... in ons IV-beleid [Informatie Voorziening-beleid] staat keurig netjes dat data geen kostenpost maar een waarde createur is, hè, een prachtig statement, maar ja als je er vervolgens geen euro aan uit wil geven dan ...” [Participant 2]

Further related to both a lacking data culture, top-down endorsement and, accordingly, unavailable resources, were participants mentioning the difficulties of establishing the true value of data governance practices as there often is an indirect relation between the value that data governance practices create. Illustrating this, participants said:

“... it is very difficult, and I am also asking for major investments in data architecture. And how will the student benefit from having your data architecture in order? That is an indirect relationship... So that is very difficult.” [Participant 2]

“... dat is heel lastig, en daarbij vraag ik om grote investeringen op data architectuur. En wat wordt de student daar beter van, als je de data architectuur op orde hebt? Dat is een indirecte relatie... Dus dat is heel lastig.” [Participant 2]

“Data remains something that is vague, in perception. An application can be imagined, you can link budget to it, you can link value to it. Truly seeing data as an asset and using it as such is extremely difficult.” [Participant 3]

“Data blijft in perceptie iets vaags. Een applicatie daar kan men zich iets bij voorstellen, daar kun je budget aan koppelen, daar kun je waarde aan koppelen. Data écht als een asset zien en ook zo gebruiken, dat is ontzettend moeilijk.” [Participant 3]

The aforementioned challenges related to the prerequisites underlying ownership model implementations and were seen as most pressing by many of the participants. While organisational challenges related to incoherent and siloed or immature ownership model

implementations were perhaps perceived as less pressing, they were nonetheless present and acknowledged. Fragmented assignment of ownership model roles led to difficulties in establishing who was accountable and responsible when a data-related issue occurred. Moreover, lacking formalisation of roles and coordinative designs between roles led to vague expectations and ambiguities as to who had a mandate in certain situations. Furthermore, lacking ownership models and the presence of siloed data domains led to data quality problems, coordinative problems, inefficient data warehousing (i.e. higher costs) and, in some cases, even led to data breaches, as argued by one participant when asked: “What are data ownership related challenges you encounter?”:

“... the silos in which work is done. I also think that data owners do not know what their relationship to each other's domain is, within the data structure that is there. ... everyone is in their own silo so that very little is actually centrally arranged ... in a formal way. Because informally people may know where to find each other and that has its charm, but for an organisation as large as this [organisation], that charm is quickly lost when you have to deal with data breaches, of course.” [Participant 1]

“... de silo's waarin gewerkt wordt. Ik denk ook dat de data eigenaren niet weten van elkaar wat hun relatie tot elkaars domein is, binnen de data structuur die er is. ... iedereen zit in zijn eigen silo, dus dat er is heel weinig eigenlijk centraal geregeld ... op een formele manier. Want informeel weten mensen elkaar misschien wel te vinden en dat heeft zo wel zijn charme, maar goed, voor een organisatie zo groot als deze [organisatie] is die charme heel snel verdwenen op het moment dat je daardoor met data-lekken te maken krijgt natuurlijk.” [Participant 1]

The latter argument should make clear that while participants deemed challenges resulting from lacking and immature or siloed ownership models less pressing, they acknowledged these challenges as causing harm nonetheless. By developing the OMIT, the author tries to enable organisations to better address these challenges. The OMIT should enable organisations to design and implement holistic ownership models from an enterprise perspective. Furthermore, the OMIT should enable organisations to design and implement ownership models while consciously considering the prerequisites underlying ownership models, so as to enhance the chance for successful implementation. The findings presented in this section therefore further strengthen the practical relevance of the OMIT.

5. Phase two: OMIT development, validation and refinement

This chapter reports on phase two of the research, thus encompassing the development of the initial OMIT, subsequently validating the initial OMIT through validation interviews and, finally, making refinements to come to the final OMIT. This chapter is therefore structured as follows. First, the development of the first OMIT version is described. This includes a stipulation of how each OMIT dimension was devised, how the concrete questions accompanying the OMIT were constructed and, finally, how the instruction sheet was designed. Finally, the findings obtained through the validation round of the OMIT, by means of expert validation interviews, are presented, including an elaboration on the necessary refinements and additions made to the final OMIT, compared to the initial OMIT version.

5.1 OMIT development: version 1

During phase two, the first step involved the development of the initial OMIT based on the inputs acquired during phase one. This section firstly includes a stipulation of the relevant OMIT dimensions, after which the formulation of concrete questions within the OMIT is discussed. Finally, the design choice and process of incorporating an instruction sheet is provided.

5.1.1 Constructing the OMIT dimensions

The starting point when constructing the OMIT was to establish the central ownership model dimensions. These dimensions are in essence a set of most important topics related to ownership models that need to be considered when assessing the current ownership model state and when developing an ownership model implementation. The central OMIT dimensions can be found in the first version of the OMIT, presented in appendix A, and are shown for clarity in table 5.

Dimensions of the first version of the OMIT	
1. Data Quality and Integrity	2. Privacy and Security
3. Risk and Compliance	4. Data Access and Usage
5. People and Culture	6. Ownership Model Design Choices
7. Prerequisites	

Table 5. OMIT dimensions (1st version).

The central dimensions in the OMIT were constructed based on the findings during phase one of the research. As these findings together led to the conceptual model shown in figure 6, provided in section 4.1, this conceptual model formed the basis for the establishment of the central OMIT dimensions. Marchildon et al. (2018) argued that during their first validation round, participants found the dimensions in their model hard to comprehend without a definition. Therefore, the design choice was made to incorporate a definition in the OMIT for each dimension. The initial OMIT version, and its dimension, can be found in appendix A.

Looking at table 5, the first five dimensions directly correspond to the central topics in the conceptual model shown in section 4.1. It was already argued elaborately that these topics are of central importance in the activities and responsibilities of ownership model participants, clearly explaining why these dimensions were included in the OMIT. Notably, the design choice was made to not include 'organisational control' in the OMIT as a separate dimension. As was explained in section 4.1, an ownership model and the central activities and responsibilities within this model can be seen as means to ensure the organisation is steered in a certain direction. This implies that when the central topics are addressed appropriately in the ownership model design and central activities and responsibilities, organisational control is part of the outcome (i.e. the organisation is 'controlled'). Along this line of reasoning, when these central topics are addressed appropriately it automatically means that organisational control is conducted, at least to some extent. It was therefore deemed unnecessary to separately incorporate organisational control as a dimension.

Turning to dimension 6, the inclusion of ownership model design choices as a separate dimension in the OMIT directly corresponds to the objectives the OMIT aims to fulfil. Partially, these objectives are in essence to enable organisations in designing, implementing and/or further improving an ownership model and related ownership model practices. The actual design choices regarding the ownership model are therefore a crucial aspect making it only logical to include it as a separate dimension in the OMIT. This sixth dimension was consciously put in sixth place in the OMIT. As the phase one interviews showed, organisations with a low ownership model maturity are often conducting ownership model practices in a less formalised manner. By letting an organisation assess its current state of ownership model practices along the first five dimensions, this organisation obtains an assessment of the (perhaps unconscious and informal) design choices that are already in place. This current state can then serve as a foundation to build upon in making conscious and formal design choices, explaining the order of dimensions.

The seventh and final dimension concerns the prerequisites that emerged from both existing literature and the primary data analysed during phase one. Interviewees emphatically argued that for ownership model practices to have a chance to succeed, these prerequisites need to be addressed at least to some extent. It was therefore deemed necessary to make organisations devote emphatic attention to these prerequisites in the assessment of their current and intended future ownership model practices, explaining the choice to include these as a separate dimension in the OMIT. Furthermore, this final dimension served perfectly as a last check for organisations to verify whether their assessment of all prior dimensions conformed to these prerequisites, explaining the placement at the end of the OMIT.

5.1.2 Formulating concrete OMIT questions

After dimensions had been constructed, placed in a conscious chronological order and were accompanied by a definition, the following step was to formulate questions for each dimension. As mentioned before, by incorporating these specific questions into the OMIT, similar to Marchildon et al. (2018), organisations are enabled to make a self-assessment with the OMIT, therefore fulfilling part of the second research objective. The concrete questions that were formulated can be found in the first version of the OMIT presented in appendix A.

A conscious design choice when constructing the concrete questions within the OMIT was to formulate open-ended questions that require a qualitative answer instead of formulating closed-ended questions that are answerable on a Likert scale similar to Merkus (2015) and Marchildon et al. (2018), the latter yielding quantitative answers. The author agrees that closed-ended Likert scale questions are useful to make an easily understandable assessment of the current state of ownership model practices as it allows the calculation of a numerical value that indicates a certain maturity level. Furthermore, repeating this process in the future allows for a comparison of maturity levels to assess whether the situation has improved. However, the author argues this method has several shortcomings. First, this method assumes equal weights of answers and therefore assumes homogeneity across organisations. Consider the third dimension of the OMIT (i.e. Risk and Compliance). Organisations that are heavily subject to legislation might put a much larger weight on this dimension compared to an organisation in a lesser-regulated industry. However, the scores calculated for each dimension do not take this aspect into account, as a score of 2.5 on dimension 3 and the same score for dimension 4 are of equal weight. Of course, such an organisation can prioritise the improvement of aspects in the third dimension over other dimensions, but the fact remains that the scores of questions answerable on a Likert scale do not address the potential differences across organisations. Second, as these questions are solely closed-ended, answers that are given do not in themselves provide much content to establish a way forward towards improvement. More concretely, scoring a 2 on a scale of 1 to 5 implies a rather low maturity but does not help much to establish how and what should be improved. Taking these shortcomings into consideration, the author argues that closed-ended Likert scale questions are useful in making an assessment and comparing progress over time, but are less useful for the actual stage of designing and/or implementing an ownership model. As the latter objectives are part of the second research objective, the author decided to formulate open-ended questions aiming to yield more meaningful qualitative answers. The manner in which questions are formulated aims to be wide enough to stimulate answering broadly and completely while aiming to remain within a reasonable scope of concreteness according to the dimension to which questions belong. This should induce users to provide complete and meaningful answers that reflect on the current state of ownership model practices and should induce to assess what aspects need to be addressed to further develop and improve these ownership model practices. In this manner, the author argues that qualitative open-ended questions are more useful in fulfilling the second research objective.

Several aspects of the collected and analysed sources during phase one of the research were combined to formulate the OMIT questions. It would go beyond a reasonable scope of explicitness to discuss how each individual question was formulated. Nevertheless, to provide the reader with a clear and complete understanding of what sources were used for each question the overview displayed in table 6 can be consulted.

	Dimension 1	Dimension 2	Dimension 3	Dimension 4	Dimension 5	Dimension 6	Dimension 7
Primary data – phase one interviews	1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.5, 1.6, 1.7, 1.8	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5	4.1a & b, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5	5.1, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5, 5.6	6.1, 6.2, 6.3, 6.4, 6.5, 6.6	7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4, 7.5
Adler (2007)	1.1, 1.3	2.1a	3.1				
Sun (2011)	1.1, 1.8	2.1a	3.1, 3.3		5.3, 5.4, 5.5	6.3	7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4
Merkus (2015)	1.5	2.7	3.4	4.1a	5.1, 5.6		
Henderson (2017)	1.6	2.1, 2.5		4.4, 4.5	5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4	6.3, 6.5	7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4, 7.5
Marchildon et al. (2018)	1.4, 1.5, 1.6, 1.8	2.3, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7	3.1, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5	4.1a, 4.4	5.1, 5.2, 5.5, 5.6	6.5	7.3, 7.4
van Gils (2020)				4.1a, 4.2, 4.5	5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4	6.2, 6.3, 6.5, 6.6	7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4, 7.5
Aarnoutse (2021)	1.6			4.1a, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5	5.1, 5.2	6.3, 6.4, 6.6	7.5
Van Nederpelt & Black (2020); Werkgroep Data Kwaliteit DAMA NL (2023)	1.1						

Table 6. Overview of sources that were used for each specific OMIT question (1st version).

As can be seen in table 6, besides the primary data collected during phase one, the DGMM developed by Marchildon et al. (2018) served as input to relatively many questions compared to other sources. The reason for this was the fact that Marchildon et al. (2018) were the sole source that had any concrete questions for organisations to self-assess, in this case, their data governance maturity. This made their tool particularly useful, not only for the format and layout of the OMIT but also for the way in which definitions and concrete questions within the OMIT were formulated, regardless of its content. For example, the lengthiness of questions and specific wording used by Marchildon et al. (2018) was used as an informal benchmark while constructing the OMIT questions.

The process of developing these questions is exemplified by illustrating how the content of certain individual questions was combined from multiple sources. Consider OMIT-question 3.1, which was formulated based on the phase one interviews, Adler (2007), Sun (2011) and Marchildon et al. (2018). In the Oracle whitepaper, Sun argues: “First and far most, it is important to understand and prioritise data governance needs. Although it may seem ideal to tackle all data issues at once, it is far more effective to target specific assets to start.” (Sun, 2011, p. 12). In line with this, Adler (2007) mentions that one of the first maturity levels is reached when critical data for regulatory and legal policies are identified, implying that identifying this kind of data should be prioritised. While reading this, the author remembered that participants during the phase one interviews had mentioned that certain organisational domains had a much more mature data management because that specific domain was subject to rather strict legislation of central importance to the organisation’s core business. Furthermore, Marchildon et al. (2018) included a specific question about a type of regulation that the organisation might be subject to: “Is your organisation subject to confidentiality regulations?” (Marchildon et al., 2018, p. 187). Combining

all these aspects, the author formulated question 3.1 where organisations assess what legislation is of central importance to the organisation's core business. Moreover, the argument by Sun (2011) that data governance needs should be prioritised and the similar line of reasoning by Adler (2007) further inspired the author in part of the formulation of questions 1.1 and 2.1a, where organisations are again led to prioritise certain artefacts.

Another example illustrating how the content of certain questions developed was the fact that the phase one interviews made it emphatically clear that especially organisations with a lower data governance maturity often have informal procedures, policies and ways of working related to ownership model practices. This led the author to include a check in the OMIT questions where organisations assess to what extent certain specific topics are formalised or not. This can be found in a total of sixteen OMIT-question, often in the last one or two questions of a dimension.

The author found that certain topics that emerged during the construction of the conceptual model shown in figure 6 were at some point in the OMIT construction only partially addressed. For example, the concrete questions in dimension 6 of the OMIT (i.e. 'Ownership Model Design Choices') were constructed to address the design choices for the ownership model scope, the design choices regarding the roles and functions and what these roles involve. However, the processes in which ownership model participants are involved were not yet addressed. Since these processes concern more general data management-related topics it would go beyond the scope of dimension 6 to address these processes only in that dimension. Furthermore, the categorisation into executive and managerial level central ownership model practices proved to be a topic too narrow and of a lower priority compared to other topics so it was not deemed appropriate to devote a separate dimension to this. Yet, this categorisation was found to be important based on both the phase one interviews and existing literature. Eventually, these considerations led the author to incorporate these aspects of the conceptual model into the existing dimensions of the OMIT. For example, the first five dimensions of the OMIT concern more general data management-related topics that are of central importance to ownership model participants. In each of these dimensions, a concrete question was included that assesses what processes are currently in place related to that dimension. Similarly, a concrete question related to the central executive ownership model activity of forming policies, again shown in the conceptual model, was included in the first five OMIT dimensions except dimension 4. Further illustrating, the managerial ownership model activity shown in the conceptual model that concerns measuring performance was incorporated in dimension 1 (question 1.8) and dimension 5 (question 5.5). Moreover, the managerial activity shown in the conceptual model of allocating roles & functions was incorporated in dimension 5 (question 5.4) and the activity of 'managing people' was generally incorporated in dimension 5. Furthermore, and finally, the executive ownership model activity shown in the conceptual model that concerns the allocation of resources and viewing data as an asset was partially incorporated in the prerequisites (i.e. dimension 7) and dimension 5 (question 5.1).

5.1.3 Incorporating an instruction sheet

While researching the aforementioned scientifically validated DGMMs (Merkus, 2015; Comuzzi & Patel, 2016; Marchildon et al., 2018), none seemed to have a section accompanying the tool itself that introduces or clarifies the tool's aspects and intended use other than the research paper itself. On the other hand, the discussed best practice DGMMs (Adler, 2007; Newman & Logan, 2008; Sun, 2011; DataFlux, n.d.) include an elaborate introduction and clarification of the DGMMs' aspects. To further facilitate self-assessment by an organisation it seemed highly appropriate to incorporate a section that introduces and clarifies the OMIT. However, the author deemed it unwise to incorporate an elaborate section as this would not enhance the practicality of the tool. Therefore, it was decided to include a compact yet informative sheet with relevant information, shown with the OMIT in appendix A. The content of this instruction sheet was mostly based on the author's considerations of potential caveats users of the OMIT might encounter. First, the objectives the OMIT aims to fulfil and the target audience of the tool are clarified. The objectives the OMIT aims to fulfil are in line with the second research objective that was mentioned before. The target audience was further specified to clarify that the user of the OMIT should pose a considerable amount of knowledge/experience in data management and/or governance while also clarifying that a single individual can't have all the necessary information to assess the OMIT, in line with Marchildon et al. (2018). Second, a set of practical instructions were provided that the author deemed important for users to be aware of before commencing with the OMIT. Finally, additional advice was included that was not deemed of high importance before commencing with the OMIT, yet was deemed potentially useful for practitioners in further guiding self-assessment with the OMIT. For example, the option to alter questions to be answerable on a Likert scale was suggested as certain organisations might find this more practical in assessing their current state of ownership model practices and comparing it over time, in line with the reasonings presented in the previous section. The combination of all these aspects resulted in the instruction sheet as shown at the end of the OMIT in appendix A.

5.2 OMIT development: final version

After the initial OMIT shown in appendix A had been developed, a total of six semi-structured interviews were conducted to validate the initial OMIT. As discussed in section 2.3.3, this involved scrutinising the initial OMIT in terms of its general clarity, overall ease of use and perceived practical relevance (i.e. its completeness, effectiveness and usefulness). This section firstly discusses the phase two validation-interview findings by illustrating how the remarks of participants were incorporated in the refined final version of the OMIT, shown in Appendix B. Following that, a brief discussion is provided on the overall perception of the OMIT by participants, focussing on the perceived effectiveness and usefulness of the OMIT. To ease this discussion, table 2 is repeated below for ease of reference.

Type of organisation	Industry	No. Employees	Function/role	Experience
2. University of applied sciences	Education	4000	Enterprise Architect	11 years
3. Educational publisher & umbrella holding company	Publishing (hard copy and software)	300 & 5000	Senior manager analytics and enterprise architect	19 years

Main function/role	Experience	Recent contributions and activities
6. Head of organisation's Data Management department	10+ years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementing Data Management on an enterprise-wide level for a publicly listed multinational organisation.
7. Founder and director of an organisation specialised in data & analytics services for digital transformations.	20+ years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Besides current company activities a track record in Business Intelligence and Data & Analytics consulting. Board activities in a renowned data management foundation.
8. Managing partner at an organisation specialised in supporting organisations in digital transformations.	15+ years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Besides current company activities a track record in consulting, research and coaching, all around bridging the fields of IT and business. Board activities in a renowned data management foundation. University professor in related fields. Author of several books in the field of data management and enterprise architecture.
9. Currently self-employed. Advisor in data management, focussing on coaching/training of professionals and consulting services.	25+ years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Besides current activities a vast track record in consulting on several projects and in roles, such as senior data officer, senior advisor and data architect. Board activities in a renowned data management foundation.

Repetition of table 2. Overview of interviewees and their professional background – research phase two.

5.2.1 Refining the OMIT

Positioning of instruction sheet

Participant 3 questioned the positioning of the instruction sheet at the end, instead of placing it at the beginning. The participant argued that the natural tendency when seeing the OMIT was to start, seemingly obvious, at the beginning by filling in the OMIT questions. As the instruction sheet contains information that users should be aware of before commencing with the OMIT questions, the placement of the instruction sheet was rightfully questioned. The author argued that the effect of not reading the instruction sheet, due to its positioning, could be detrimental to the OMIT's clarity and understanding. As the initial version of the OMIT had at that point only been sent to participant 3 the placement of the instruction sheet was altered immediately before finishing the other interviews. This was the only preliminary alteration that was made.

The ambiguity of the concept 'Ownership Model'

Several participants argued an 'Ownership Model' as a concept is ambiguous as it leaves space for differing mental images. This ambiguousness led some participants to not fully comprehend what the OMIT was about, diminishing their general understanding of the OMIT while trying to answer the concrete questions. As pointed out by Polsky (2013) and van Gils (2020), the scope of an ownership model can be defined according to different dimensions. This, in turn, gravely affects the mental image one has of what it is exactly that one has the proverbial ownership of. As the OMIT was constructed to specifically address a data ownership model and not, for example, a model incorporating process owners, a larger emphasis was placed on this in the OMIT. This encompassed adding a definition and example of an 'ownership model' within the instruction sheet, based on van Gils (2020), adjusting dimension 6 and its accompanying definition and, finally, adjusting all the individual questions that contained the term 'ownership model'.

Discussing the scope of the OMIT

When questioned about the OMIT's scope, participants seemed to be divided. Two participants argued that especially the first four dimensions of the OMIT related to general data management practices and not specifically to ownership models. However, all but one of the other participants believed that the content was within the scope of ownership model practices. The latter interviewees argued that while responsibilities and activities such as data quality management, access management, and security/compliance, are essentially general data management activities, these are central to ownership model participants. Therefore, the OMIT focuses on the central data management activities and responsibilities of ownership model participants, making it relevant to ownership models. While some participants suggested devoting a part to data management context analysis and an ownership model design part, the author ultimately decided to keep the content as is, based on the arguments of the latter experts.

Clarifying and adjusting dimensions

The usage of the term 'Integrity' in dimension 1 raised questions for participants 2 and 8. It was argued that the usage of this term evoked thoughts of topics unrelated to the intended meaning in this dimension, like the CIA-triad in information security. Participants argued that this misconception might lie in the lacking clarification of the term in the accompanying definition. Expanding this argument, participants 2, 7 and 8 argued that the way in which organisations express 'data quality', or in other words what data quality dimensions are used (Van Nederpelt & Black, 2020; Werkgroep Data Kwaliteit DAMA NL, 2023), differs per organisation, potentially yielding ambiguous interpretations of what 'data quality' means. Furthermore, it was argued that the usage of the wording 'high-quality data' in the accompanying definition can yield ambiguous interpretations as what is deemed 'high' differs both per organisation and per specific domain or scenario. Addressing these arguments, the author adjusted the definition within dimension 1 to better reflect the intended meaning of 'integrity', to clarify how data quality can be expressed and to steer away from level-laden terminology.

Turning to dimensions 2 and 3, participants scrutinised the clarity of the dimensions and accompanying definitions in several ways. Several participants argued that the second and third dimensions both concern content that is related to one another. While one participant questioned whether the adopted combination of concepts (i.e. privacy & security and risk & compliance) is the most appropriate choice, other participants seemed to agree with this combination and specifically mentioned that the content contained in the dimensions was in fact complementary and mutually reinforcing. However, several other caveats were provided related to these dimensions. First, the wording 'all data' in the definition of dimension 2 implies that literally all data should be kept secure and confidential. While it seems reasonable that most organisational data should be kept secure, it is not the case that literally all organisational data should be kept confidential. As only confidential or sensitive data should be kept confidential, which is what this dimension aims at, the wording in the definition of dimension 2 was changed accordingly. Second, the usage of 'privacy' in the same definition narrows the scope to data related to persons, while the dimensions' scope is broader than this. Therefore, the dimension was adjusted to 'Confidentiality and Security', notably in line with Marchildon et al. (2018). Finally, it was argued that combining 'risk and compliance' in dimension 3 and the usage of 'data security risks' in its accompanying definition narrowed the scope to only data-related security risks and created the impression that only compliance risks are addressed in this dimension. Participants noted that other types of risks should also be addressed in an organisation's data management/governance practices, like financial risks due to inadequate data management for example. To address these arguments, adjustments were made to the definition of dimension 3.

Considering dimension 4, participant 8 argued that using the terms 'requesting' and 'providing' in the definition for 'data access' unintentionally includes security-related practices that have to do with authorisations and/or confidentiality of data. While question 4.1b does specifically question aim to address this aspect, dimension 4 generally aims to assess the specific methods, processes and systems that are in place within the organisation for data recipients that want to use a certain dataset (e.g. how can they find and gain access to this?). To better account for this, the definition was altered slightly. Moreover, the wording of some of the questions was altered to account for this.

Finally, participant 7 argued that it remained unclear in dimension 6 what the actual ownership model design choices were. Considering the current enumeration in the accompanying definition (i.e. "forming role or function names, establishing their responsibilities, drawing the actual model and so forth."), the interviewee argued that this left it unclear that the concrete questions following in dimension 6 are in fact the central ownership model design choices that need to be considered. Therefore, this short enumeration was replaced by a more emphatic explanation that the questions in dimension 6 concern the actual design choices.

Clarifying and adjusting existing OMIT-questions

Participants were first asked to assess the OMIT questions based on their clarity and general ease of understanding. Second, interviewees were asked to consider the content of the questions and assess their practical relevance within the scope of the OMIT. Multiple adjustments were made to increase the clarity of existing questions. Only two changes were made to existing questions to further specify the content within the questions. Next to that, several questions were expanded into sub-questions and several new questions were added to expand already addressed content and to further address inadequately addressed content. It would go beyond a reasonable scope to elaborate on all the alterations that were made. The overview displayed in table 7 is provided to illustrate what questions were altered and to indicate the underlying reason for the alteration. The added (sub)questions are discussed in the following section.

When questions were added the chronological ordering of questions was altered as well. At the same time, this implied that the numbering of certain questions was altered compared to the first OMIT version. In table 7, singular arrows are used to indicate the change in question number, where 1.1 → 1.1a simply means that question 1.1 in the first OMIT version was changed into question 1.1a in the second OMIT version. Only those questions that were altered to improve the clarity and content and were subsequently affected in their numbering by the added (sub)questions are displayed in this manner in table 7. Taking 1.1 → 1.1a under as an example again, this means question 1.1 from the first OMIT-version was adjusted for clarity and, later, changed into sub-question 1.1a due to the extra question 1.1b being added.

	Adjustments for clarity	Adjustments to address content	Added (sub)questions
Dimension 1	1.1 → 1.1a, 1.2, 1.3, 1.5, 1.6		1.1b, 1.7
Dimension 2	2.2, 2.3, 2.6 → 2.7	2.5, 2.6 → 2.7 2.7 → 2.8	2.6
Dimension 3	3.2, 3.3		3.4, 3.7
Dimension 4	4.3	4.1a	4.1c, 4.1d 4.5 → 4.5a, 4.5b
Dimension 5	5.3, 5.4		5.5b
Dimension 6	6.3, 6.4, 6.6a		6.3
Dimension 7	7.5		7.1b, 7.1c

Table 7. Overview of adjusted OMIT-questions.

Several examples are discussed to illustrate how questions were adjusted based on the assessment of participants. Consider questions 1.2, 2.2, 3.2 and 4.3. These questions aim to assess data classification within an organisation according to the dimension each question belongs to. Participants argued that currently, only question 1.2 asked to what extent data had been classified and that the latter questions only asked how the current state of data classification influenced

related issues. This creates an imparity between the questions where question 1.2 in essence asks something different than the other questions, which was not intended by the author. Moreover, participants argued that data classification is always done according to a certain category or dimension, while none of these questions specifically seemed to consider this. To address these concerns, questions were adjusted to reflect that all questions aim to assess how data is currently classified and to more emphatically reflect that each question aims to assess data classification according to the OMIT dimension that specific question belongs to.

While the former example illustrated that multiple questions were adjusted, also simpler alterations were made. For example, one participant argued for question 4.4 that the usage of the term 'data transmissions' could be associated with the technology behind data transferring, distracting from the simpler intended meaning of merely sharing data. Similarly, one participant argued it remained unclear that question 3.3 aimed to assess the alignment of data management practices with general organisational risk management. The participant argued that merely using the term 'risk management' within a tool for data ownership models could lead users to believe 'data-related risk management' was meant. To address these concerns, it sufficed to adjust and expand the terms that led to ambiguous interpretations.

Considering question 2.5, several participants argued that just discussing 'encryption' as a security measure for sensitive data is rather specific as there are many more measures and methods that can be considered. Several concrete examples were provided, like the NIST- and ISO 27001 standards. To address these concerns voiced by the interviewees, question 2.5 was altered to encompass a broader spectrum of security methods, incorporating the concrete examples that participants mentioned. Following that, since question 2.5 now contained examples of industry standards and question 2.6 considered organisational standards, question 2.6 (later changed to question 2.7 in the second OMIT version) was expanded to prevent ambiguous interpretations.

The second content-related change that was made to an existing OMIT question related to question 4.1a. Participant 2 argued that in dimension 4, questions seemed to assume that when a data recipient retrieves or requests a dataset, the dataset is simply provided. The interviewee said this seems to forgo an intermediary step since a dataset is often prepared or even created upon a data recipient's request. While the author did consider this to be part of the process of data access and usage, it was not made explicit in the questions. Therefore, question 4.1a was altered to incorporate a clarification, explicitly addressing the aforementioned argument. The aforementioned examples should illustrate how both larger and minor adjustments were made to improve the clarity and content of questions.

Adding (sub)questions to address content

As mentioned in the previous section, for certain OMIT questions, several participants provided arguments to either alter the content of a question in its current form or argued that certain topics were currently missing in the OMIT questions. To appropriately address these concerns, several (sub)questions were added, shown in table 7 in the section before.

Related to question 1.1 in the first version of the OMIT, several participants argued that merely establishing data quality dimensions that are essential to the organisation ignores the fact that appropriate data quality dimensions will differ per specific organisational domain or scenario in which data is needed. Moreover, the appropriate targeted level of data quality will differ per specific scenario as well. Therefore, question 1.1 was split, where question 1.1 became 1.1a and question 1.1b was added to address the concern described above. Next to that, participant 8 argued that the usage of reference data was lacking, as dimension 1 also aims to address the integrity of data. Reference data is often inadequately addressed and governed in organisations due to low prioritisation compared to other activities, even though the usage of reference data can be of great importance to data integrity. To address these arguments by participant 8, question 1.7 was added.

Turning to dimension 2, participant 9 argued that organisations often assign confidentiality or sensitivity labels to an entire dataset or system, while it in fact rarely happens that the entire dataset or system concerns truly sensitive content. Oftentimes, specific parts of datasets/systems or even specific records within a dataset can be considered sensitive while the rest of the dataset can/should not. If the entire set or system is then considered to be sensitive, potentially useful content is shielded unnecessarily. Furthermore, the participant argued that this tendency is especially present for datasets of secondary usage. To address these arguments, question 2.6 was added to dimension 2.

When pondering dimension 3, participant 8 argued that while dimension 2 contained questions related to (data) security measures, questions related to (security) risk assessments were missing. The interviewee argued that such a risk assessment often is or should be the basis for security measures that are subsequently taken. Therefore, to address this, question 3.4 was added. Next to these remarks, several participants argued that organisations have often not considered the potential effects of changing legislation on their data management practices. This closely fits the remarks of another participant that oftentimes data governance/management is arranged in a reactive manner while preventive solutions are present to a lesser extent or mostly present in more mature organisations. To that extent, question 3.7 was added to dimension 3.

Considering dimension 4, several questions were added. First, several interviewees mentioned the importance of transparency and traceability of alterations in the process of data access and usage. Participants argued this aspect seemed to be missing in the current questions, even though organisations often struggle with this aspect and/or inappropriately address this topic. Following this, question 4.1c was added as a sub-question. Second, participant 9 argued that secondary usage of data within organisations was not appropriately addressed in the OMIT. For dimension 2, these concerns were addressed by altering questions 2.7 and 2.8 and, partially, in the added question 2.6. For dimension 4, the secondary usage of data poses challenges as well, mostly related to the aforementioned importance of transparency and traceability of alterations. While many organisations have a grip on the traceability of primary-used data through the process of data access and usage, this applies less so for secondary-used data. To incorporate these arguments, question 4.1d was added as a sub-question. Finally, participant 9 argued it varies

substantially per organisation how DSA's are created, logged, enacted and so on. Similarly, the content and format of the DSA may differ as well. Moreover, participant 9 argued it sometimes remains unclear what to do in practice after a DSA has been established. The latter point closely relates to how an organisation works with their DSAs. For example, if the DSA is not centrally logged or accessible it may be hard to retrieve or when the DSA contains very little information it may not provide enough content to be useful in practice. Based on this, question 4.5 was split into question 4.5a, after which question 4.5b was added to address these caveats in the OMIT.

Participant 9 further mentioned that it would fit the spirit of the fifth dimension well to incorporate the usage of KPIs, talked about in question 5.5, for the development of data ownership model participants both on a personal and functional level. Therefore, question 5.5 was split into 5.5a, after which question 5.5b was added to address this argument.

As was mentioned before, participant 9 argued that secondary usage of data within organisations was not appropriately addressed in the OMIT. The interviewee mentioned organisations often, depending on their maturity levels, have a rather clear division of accountabilities and responsibilities related to primary-used data while this is far less the case for secondary-used data. To further address these concerns so far done in questions 2.6, 2.7, 2.8 and 4.1d, question 6.3 was added to dimension 6.

Finally, considering dimension 7, participants 8 and 9 argued that besides executive-level endorsement, also operational-level endorsement was of grave importance to the success of data management/governance practices within an organisation. While the established prerequisites in the OMIT specifically considered executive-level endorsement to be crucial, sub-question 7.1c was added to incorporate these arguments. Moreover, several participants argued that executive-level endorsement is often voiced but not truly substantiated in executive decisions/actions or by actually providing mandate for such decisions/actions. To address these concerns, sub-question 7.1b was added, concluding the discussion of all (sub)questions that were added to the OMIT.

Altering the instruction sheet

All but one participant agreed that the instruction sheet can in potence provide added value to the OMIT. However, participants argued that the instruction sheet in its current form has several shortcomings. Several participants mentioned that while browsing through the OMIT, difficulties and caveats were encountered, such as not knowing how to answer questions, not knowing what type of answers were expected, not knowing what the end result should be and doubting whether questions are answerable by more general users. Potentially explaining this, all but two participants argued that for the tool to enable organisations to self-assess their ownership model practices the introduction and the instructions are rather brief and incomplete. Extending this argument, participant 3 argued that a lacking clarification of the context in which the OMIT was developed complicated the understanding of the overall tool, which even resulted in the specifically mentioned objectives and target audience being forgotten halfway through the tool. Similarly, participants 2, 3 and 6 argued that a lacking introduction to the format of the OMIT and not explaining what is meant by the 'data ownership model dimensions' further complexified their

understanding of the tool. Finally, in line with the aforementioned arguments, participants argued that adding the additional advice of transforming questions to be answerable on a Likert scale is potentially useful but unclear in its current form.

To address all of the aforementioned arguments that were voiced by participants, the instruction sheet was gravely altered. First, a more elaborate but still concise introduction was devised that explains the context in which the OMIT was devised. Furthermore, in line with what was mentioned before, this introduction includes a clarification and example of a 'data ownership model' to address the ambiguity of this concept. Second, an elaboration on the intended use of the OMIT was constructed. Here, the existing OMIT objectives were incorporated but adjusted slightly in certain terminology to address the perceived unclarity for participants. This perceived unclarity was further addressed by adding an overview of the OMIT dimensions and introducing the format of the tool. Third, the target audience was introduced in a less static and more narrative-style manner. The same holds for the header, which was altered to "Who is the OMIT intended for?" to be more emphatic and eye-catching for users while referring back to the instruction sheet after commencing with the tool. Fourth, a section was added to the instruction sheet that explains how the OMIT should be used. This includes an elaboration on the thought process that the questions try to provoke, how questions are expected to be answered and, in turn, how the provided answers can be utilised after finalising the self-assessment. Finally, a more elaborate and complete explanation was given regarding the additional advice of answering questions on a Likert scale, including an example of how this could be done for a specific question, a clearer overview of potential Likert scale answer options and instruction on how to calculate the according maturity scores. Making these alterations should appropriately address the shortcomings of the instruction sheet that were voiced by participants.

5.2.2 Perceived effectiveness and usefulness of the OMIT

Participants were generally enthusiastic about the tool. Related to the ease of use and clarity of the OMIT, participants argued that the dimensions and questions were clear and answerable, apart from the use of certain terminology and ambiguous formulations which were just discussed and adjusted accordingly. Several participants mentioned they liked how the way in which questions were formulated induced broad and reflective thinking on organisational ownership model practices. Furthermore, the content of the OMIT, again apart from the aforementioned adjustments, was deemed practically relevant for the intended audience and generally within the scope of ownership model participants. Finally, participants argued that the OMIT served as a rather complete and appropriate checklist for organisations looking to design and/or implement an ownership model or looking to address data ownership-related issues within the organisation. This implied that the OMIT was deemed effective in fulfilling at least part of the intended goals.

It should be clear that while participants generally responded positively when assessing the OMIT, several caveats were provided too. These are discussed in chapter 6 when discussing the research.

6 Conclusion & discussion

This chapter concludes the report on the research. First, the conclusion to the research questions is provided, which includes a summarising reflection on the overall research. Second, a discussion of the results is given, including a discussion of the potential limitations of both the research and the resulting OMIT.

6.1 Conclusion

Due to a lacking body of existing practical tools to be used during ownership model development, implementation and/or further improvement, let alone scientifically validated practical tools, organisations seem to encounter challenges when developing or implementing such a model. This research aimed to address these practical challenges by developing a scientifically validated practical tool to be used during the design, implementation and/or further improvement of an organisational ownership model and related ownership model practices.

Following from the centrality of artefact construction during this research, a Design Science Research approach, based on Hevner (2007), was adopted as the overarching research design. Following this, the research was divided into two phases. During the first phase of the research, through an extensive literature review and primary interviews with employees working in data management/governance or enterprise architecture within five different organisations, the following first main research question was answered:

Main RQ1: What conceptual basis can be established to assist in developing the OMIT, to address the challenges organisations face when developing and implementing ownership models?

To answer this question, first, initial definitions and characteristics of concepts central to ownership models and related ownership model practices were stipulated, as to answer SQ1.

Second, to enable answering SQ2, the conceptual basis was laid to determine how organisational challenges related to ownership models could be established during the interviews. Based on the phase one interview findings, organisational challenges seemed to mostly relate to topics other than the ownership model within the organisation. Organisational challenges followed from low organisational data literacy, a lacking data-driven culture, lacking top-down endorsement and, finally, incoherent/siloed or immature ownership model implementations.

Third, to enable answering SQ3, the conceptual basis was laid to determine how differences in ownership model maturity could be established during the interviews. Following from the phase one interviews, ownership model maturities differed extensively across organisations. Smaller organisations seemed to have lower ownership model maturities compared to larger organisations. This was reflected by the fact that smaller organisations generally did not have a formal ownership model, had informal and fragmented ownership model roles in place and generally assessed data quality to be low. Next to that, the maturity of specific ownership model aspects differed widely both between and within organisations. Finally,

substantiating the practical relevance of the research, all organisations were in various stages of an ongoing transition towards data management and, hence, ownership model practices from an enterprise perspective.

Fourth, existing practical tools were identified that could assist in the development of the OMIT, to answer SQ4. It was shown that Data Governance Maturity Models, or DGMMs, are of potential use. These models serve as a practical data governance model aiming to assess an organisation's data governance practices along several dimensions. While DGMMs were useful as a concept and served as the basis for the OMIT, they showed several shortcomings. First, the models were mostly based on best practices and therefore lacked scientific validation. Second, apart from Marchildon et al. (2018), none of these models offer actual concrete tools that allow organisations to self-assess their governance practices, rendering them less practical. Moreover, and finally, no practical models specifically targeting ownership models could be identified. Building on these findings, the OMIT was constructed to incorporate concrete questions that allow organisational self-assessment.

Fifth, a conceptual model was devised, based on an extensive literature review and the aforementioned primary interviews, illustrating the relevant central ownership model characteristics, therefore answering SQ5. It was shown that ownership models are in essence a model aiming to distribute data-related accountabilities, responsibilities and activities, based on certain roles, in a formalised manner. Moreover, several central topics and prerequisites for successful ownership model implementations were identified. Combining these findings into the conceptual model discussed in chapter 4, also addressing the organisational challenges established in SQ2, served as the basis for the first OMIT-version, therefore answering the first main RQ.

During the second phase of the research, the following second main research question was answered:

Main RQ2: How can an empirically validated OMIT be developed to address the challenges organisations face when developing and implementing ownership models?

To answer this question, first, SQs 6 and 7 were answered based on the conceptual model devised during the first phase of the research. Following from the answer to SQ6 and SQ7, the initial version of the OMIT was developed, shown in appendix A.

To further improve and refine the initial OMIT, empirical and scientific validation was carried out by conducting six validation interviews with experts in the field of data management/governance and enterprise architecture. These experts had a proven expert background in their respective fields through numerous reputable activities. The phase two validation-interview findings were generally positive. Experts generally perceived the OMIT to be clear and answerable, apart from several particular instances. Moreover, experts deemed the OMIT and its content practically relevant for its intended audience and deemed the tool at least partially effective in fulfilling the intended goals. Refinements of the OMIT dimensions and existing questions were made to improve overall clarity and to reduce ambiguousness. Moreover, inadequately addressed topics were more appropriately addressed by altering the content of

existing questions and by adding several new (sub)questions into the OMIT. By addressing the arguments made by experts in the field related to the initial OMIT, thus constructing the final OMIT version shown in appendix B, SQ8 was answered. Finally, this concluded the answer to the second main research question.

6.2 Discussing the research

The interviews conducted during both research phases confirmed that data governance and data management are gaining ground in many organisations, while the maturity of these capabilities is generally still low. While the specific source of organisational challenges related to data governance and ownership models was not substantiated, challenges related to ownership model practices are present nonetheless. By addressing these challenges organisations generally face, by incorporating these in the developed OMIT, the OMIT potentially contributes to organisational efforts of solving related challenges. Moreover, by incorporating the most relevant ownership model characteristics in the OMIT, based on both primary data and an extensive literature review, the OMIT potentially contributes to the design and (further) implementation of an organisational ownership model. Substantiating these arguments, the phase two validation interviews generally confirmed that experts deem the OMIT practically relevant and effective in guiding the development and (further) implementation of an ownership model and related practices. Therefore, the implications of the OMIT for practitioners aiming to design, implement and/or improve an ownership model are verified to be positive, strengthening the results of the research.

Considering the limited scope of the research, a diverse as possible range of organisations was included in the development of the OMIT, both in terms of being private versus public, organisational size, sector and ownership model maturity, to increase the generalisability of the results. However, the scope of the research only allowed for the inclusion of five organisations in establishing relevant ownership model characteristics, besides the conducted literature review, restricting the generalisability of the results. Generalisability was further partially addressed by validating the OMIT with experts in data governance that have gained their expertise in, and still are active in many different organisations. This implies their judgement of the OMIT should be capable of assessing the relevance and effectiveness for a variety of organisations, which was confirmed to be positive in general. This implies that the resulting OMIT should be useable by a relatively diverse range of organisations with differing levels of ownership model maturities. However, the reader should bear in mind that the generalisability of results is restricted nonetheless. To address these concerns, future research could be conducted within several diverse organisations that are looking to design, implement and/or improve their ownership model, where the OMIT is utilised to assist in doing so. The research should then focus on further assessing the effectiveness in helping these organisations with their ownership model design/implementation and whether this effectiveness differs for differing organisations.

Similarly, as was mentioned before, the limited scope of the research did not allow adopting an approach of going through multiple rounds of validation nor was it possible to request participants to make a test assessment of the OMIT. The latter aspect weakens the validity of the

results, as it was not confirmed by testing in practice whether the OMIT is actually effective in the design and/or implementation of an ownership model. The expert validation interviews during phase two of the research served to address these concerns. However, as these interviews merely questioned participants' perceptions of the OMIT's effectiveness rather than their actual practical experiences while utilising the OMIT, the validity of the OMIT should be considered restricted. The aforementioned recommendation for future research would further contribute to addressing these concerns.

Apart from the methodological considerations for the generalisability and validity of the research results, several caveats and limitations related to the clarity, useability and content of the OMIT can be identified. First, several participants during the phase two validation interviews questioned why the DAMA wheel (Henderson, 2017), being the golden standard for current data management practices, was not in some way included in the OMIT. The author made a conscious decision while developing the OMIT to not base the OMIT on the DAMA-wheel, as the scope of the OMIT (i.e. ownership models and related practices) is more restricted than the scope of the DAMA-wheel, which encompasses data management in its entirety. However, participants argued that the topics contained within the OMIT questions could in fact be linked to most of the parts of the DAMA wheel. Participants argued that linking the OMIT questions to this wheel would gravely improve the clarity of used terminology and definitions, improving the overall clarity and useability of the tool. This would be an aspect to address in future research and/or refinements of the OMIT.

Second, one of the prerequisites for ownership model success concerns addressing the ownership model holistically, meaning as part of the overall data management/governance framework. To raise awareness of this, additional advice is provided in the OMIT to use the OMIT in conjunction with other practical (assessment) tools, like data governance maturity tools. However, rightfully noted during the phase two validation interviews, lacking available resources (i.e. time, money, manpower) renders the usage of the OMIT by organisations in conjunction with other practical tools less likely at the very minimum. While this prerequisite was also addressed in dimension 7 of the OMIT, the fact that many organisations might not use the OMIT in conjunction with other practical tools potentially reduces the holisticness of the OMIT.

Third, the aforementioned lacking assessment with the OMIT in practice restricted making final refinements of the OMIT in terms of clarity useability. As one participant during the phase two validation-interviews argued:

“Bruikbaarheid valt of staat met een goede uitleg, met een goede context erbij. ... Wat nog handig is om te doen, is te kijken of je uiteindelijk ook een soort voorbeeld kan geven. Zo van: ‘Als ik dit nou heb ingevuld, hoe ziet dat er dan uit? Dat zou het nog een stuk duidelijker maken.” [Participant 6]

“Usability stands or falls with a good explanation, with a good context. ... Another useful thing to do is to see if you can eventually give some kind of example. Like: ‘When I have filled this [the OMIT] in, what will it look like? That would make it even clearer.” [Participant 6]

Several experts seemed to agree, indicating that while the OMIT does allow self-assessment through the concrete questions per dimension, self-assessability is complicated by the fact that a lacking example of the OMIT reduces its clarity and overall useability. Again, by conducting research in the future where several organisations utilise the OMIT to assist in designing, implementing and/or improving their ownership model, these concerns could be addressed. This would be done by constructing a concrete example of a final result after OMIT assessment, based on the conducted assessments in several organisations.

Finally, further scrutinising the self-assessability of the OMIT, several experts said that even after multiple validation and refinement phases of the OMIT, truly diminishing the potential ambiguities and unclarities stemming from specific terminologies, definitions and differing interpretations would be next to impossible. Arguments were provided for the development of an in-house training on how to use the OMIT within organisations. However, deeming it necessary to follow training before assessing with the OMIT would defeat the purpose of truly enabling organisational self-assessment with just the OMIT. A more appropriate potential solution would be to formulate an FAQ list addressing the most encountered questions and challenges in practice when assessing with the OMIT. Digitalisation of the OMIT could potentially be useful for this, as the inclusion of '?'- or 'i'-buttons or hyperlinks could create a clear and easily accessible overview. Future research focussing on the actual assessment with the OMIT in practice could further serve to establish these most encountered questions and challenges, aiming to strengthen the potential for organisational self-assessment with the tool.

References

1. Aarnoutse, S. H. P. (2021). *Data usership under governance: a proposal for data governance roles from a usership perspective within the context of a Dutch national bank* [Msc thesis]. Radboud University Nijmegen.
2. Abraham, R., Schneider, J., & Vom Brocke, J. (2019). Data governance: A conceptual framework, structured review, and research agenda. *International Journal of Information Management*, 49, 424-438.
3. Adler, S. (2007). The IBM data governance council maturity model: building a roadmap for effective data governance. *Somers, NY, USA: IBM Corporation*.
4. Alhassan, I., Sammon, D., & Daly, M. (2016). Data governance activities: an analysis of the literature. *Journal of Decision Systems*, 25(sup1), 64-75.
5. Van Alstyne, M., Brynjolfsson, E., & Madnick, S. (1995). Why not one big database? Principles for data ownership. *Decision Support Systems*, 15(4), 267-284.
6. Benfeldt, O., Persson, J. S., & Madsen, S. (2020). Data governance as a collective action problem. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 22(2), 299-313.
7. Bleijenbergh, I. L. (2016). *Kwalitatief onderzoek in organisaties* (2nd edition). Amsterdam: Boom Uitgevers.
8. Boeije, H. (2010). *Analysis in qualitative research*. Sage publications.
9. Comuzzi, M., & Patel, A. (2016). How organisations leverage big data: A maturity model. *Industrial management & Data systems*.
10. DataFlux. (n.d.). *The Data Governance Maturity Model: Establishing the People, Policies and Technology That Manage Enterprise Data*. Retrieved October 12, 2022, from https://www.fstech.co.uk/fst/whitepapers/The_Data_Governance_Maturity_Model.pdf
11. Firican, G. (n.d.). *Data governance maturity models – Kalido*. Retrieved October 12, 2022, from <https://www.lightsondata.com/data-governance-maturity-models-kalido/>
12. Gartner. (2021, August). *A Data and Analytics Leader's Guide to Data Literacy*. Retrieved January 10, 2023, from <https://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/a-data-and-analytics-leaders-guide-to-data-literacy>
13. van Gils, B. (2020). *Data Management: A gentle introduction: Balancing theory and practice*. Van Haren.
14. Gregory, A. (2011). Data governance—Protecting and unleashing the value of your customer data assets. *Journal of Direct, Data and Digital Marketing Practice*, 12(3), 230-248.
15. Harrison, T., Pardo, T., Gasco-Hernandez, M., & Canestraro, D. (2018, January). The salience and urgency of enterprise data management in the public sector. In *Proceedings of the 51st Hawaii international conference on system sciences*.
16. Henderson, D. (2017). *DAMA DMBOK – Data Management Body of Knowledge* (Second). Technics Publications.
17. Hevner, A. R., March, S. T., Park, J., & Ram, S. (2004). Design science in information systems research. *MIS quarterly*, 75-105.
18. Hevner, A. R. (2007). A three cycle view of design science research. *Scandinavian journal of information systems*, 19(2), 4.

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19. Hevner, A., & Chatterjee, S. (2010). Design science research in information systems. In *Design research in information systems*. Springer, Boston, MA.
 20. IT Governance Institute. (2005). *Cobit 4.0: control objectives, management guidelines, maturity models*. IT Governance Institute. Rolling Meadows, IL.
 21. Jonker, R. A., Tegelaar, J. A. C., & Geurtsen, J. M. B. (2012). *Enterprise Data Management: nut en noodzaak*. Retrieved May 31, 2022, from <https://www.compact.nl/articles/enterprise-data-management-nut-en-noodzaak/>.
 22. Khatri, V., & Brown, C. V. (2010). Designing data governance. *Communications of the ACM*, 53(1), 148-152.
 23. Marchildon, P., Bourdeau, S., Hadaya, P., & Labissière, A. (2018). Data governance maturity assessment tool: A design science approach. *Projectics/Proyética/Projectique*, 20(2), 155-193.
 24. Merkus, J. R. (2015). Data Governance Maturity Model.
 25. Merriam-Webster. (n.d.-a). *Owner*. Retrieved November 2, 2022, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/owner>
 26. Merriam-Webster. (n.d.-b). *Ownership*. Retrieved November 2, 2022, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/ownership>
 27. Morewedge, C. K., Shu, L. L., Gilbert, D. T., & Wilson, T. D. (2009). Bad riddance or good rubbish? Ownership and not loss aversion causes the endowment effect. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 45(4), 947-951.
 28. van Nederpelt, P., & Black, A. (2020). Dimensions of Data Quality (DDQ). *Research Paper DAMA NL*. Retrieved January 5, 2023, from <https://www.dama-nl.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/DDQ-Dimensions-of-Data-Quality-Research-Paper-version-1.2-d.d.-3-Sept-2020.pdf>
 29. Newman, D., & Logan, D. (2008). Gartner introduces the EIM maturity model. *Gartner Research Publication, ID*, (G00160425).
 30. Otto, B. (2011a). A morphology of the organisation of data governance.
 31. Otto, B. (2011b). Organizing data governance: Findings from the telecommunications industry and consequences for large service providers. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 29(1), 3.
 32. Oxford Learner's Dictionaries. (n.d.). *Data*. Retrieved October 4, 2022, from <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/data?q=data>
 33. Pierce, J. L., Kostova, T., & Dirks, K. T. (2001). Toward a theory of psychological ownership in organizations. *Academy of Management Review*, 27, 298-310
 34. Polsky, A. (2013). *Data stewardship on the ground, notes from the field* [Presentation at the Data Governance Conference in London].
 35. Proença, D., & Borbinha, J. (2018). Maturity models for data and information management. In *International conference on theory and practice of digital libraries* (pp. 81-93). Springer, Cham.
 36. Rowley, J. (2007). The wisdom hierarchy: representations of the DIKW hierarchy. *Journal of information science*, 33(2), 163-180.

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37. Schilling, R., Aier, S., Winter, R., & Haki, K. (2020, January). Design dimensions for enterprise-wide data management: a Chief Data Officer's journey. In *Proceedings of the 53rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*.
 38. Southehal, P. (2022, June). *Data Culture: What It Is And How To Make It Work*. Retrieved March 28, 2023, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2022/06/27/data-culture-what-it-is-and-how-to-make-it-work/>
 39. Spacey, J. (2017, September). *6 Examples of a Data Owner*. Retrieved November 5, 2022, from <https://simplicable.com/new/data-owner>
 40. Statista Research Department. (May, 2022a). *Volume of data/information created, captured, copied, and consumed worldwide from 2010 to 2025, by region*. Retrieved June 1, 2022, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/871513/worldwide-data-created/>.
 41. Statista Research Department. (May, 2022b). *Leading banks in the Netherlands in 2021, by total assets*. Retrieved June 1, 2022, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/762148/leading-banks-in-the-netherlands-by-total-assets/>
 42. Stedman, C. (2021, October). *Data silo*. Retrieved September 8, 2022, from <https://www.techtarget.com/searchdatamanagement/definition/data-silo>
 43. Sun, H. (2011). *An Oracle White Paper on Enterprise Architecture - Enterprise Information Management: Best Practices in Data Governance*. Retrieved October 12, 2022, from <https://www.oracle.com/assets/oea-best-practices-data-gov-1357848.pdf>
 44. Tableau. (n.d.). *Enterprise Data Management Explained: What It Is and How It Works*. Retrieved June 1, 2022, from <https://www.tableau.com/learn/articles/enterprise-data-management>.
 45. Tallon, P. P., Ramirez, R. V., & Short, J. E. (2013). The information artifact in IT governance: Toward a theory of information governance. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 30(3), 141-178.
 46. Thuan, N. H., Drechsler, A., & Antunes, P. (2019). Construction of design science research questions. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 44(1), 20.
 47. Wang, Y. Y. R., Storey, V., & Firth, C. (1993). *Data quality research: a framework, survey, and analysis*. Total Data Quality Management Research Program, Sloan School of Management, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
 48. Weber, K., Otto, B., & Österle, H. (2009). One size does not fit all---a contingency approach to data governance. *Journal of Data and Information Quality (JDIQ)*, 1(1), 1-27.
 49. Werkgroep Data Kwaliteit DAMA NL. (2023, January). *Dimensions of Data Quality*. Retrieved January 5, 2023, from <https://dama-nl.org/dimensions-of-data-quality-en/>
 50. Zagoudis, S. (2021, May). *Defining Principles, Elements, and Roles and Responsibilities in a Data Governance Policy*. Retrieved November 6, 2022, from <https://www.dataversity.net/defining-principles-elements-and-roles-and-responsibilities-in-a-data-governance-policy/>

Appendix A - 1st version of the OMIT

(Format, layout and formulation of definitions based on Marchildon et al. (2018))

1st Dimension - Data Quality and Integrity
<p>The <i>Data Quality and Integrity</i>-dimension concerns those methods and practices undertaken by the organisation to ensure all data is of high quality and integrity. By all data, we mean data from all sources and in all content formats. By high quality data, we mean data that meets certain requirements or quality standards.</p>
<p>Question 1.1 To what extent have data quality dimensions been established that are essential for the organisation?¹</p>
<p>Question 1.2 To what extent has (essential) data been classified and to what extent and in what way does the current state of data classification influence data quality issues?</p>
<p>Question 1.3 What datasets and golden sources are crucial for the organisation's core business and its management information and to what extent do these exhibit data quality issues?</p>
<p>Question 1.4 Are data quality issues documented and to what extent are they being used as inputs for developing solutions?</p>
<p>Question 1.5 What (technical) processes are currently in place to ensure high quality data and to what extent are these processes formalised?</p>
<p>Question 1.6 To what extent is business/domain modelling deployed and has a data glossary, catalogue and/or dictionary been established?</p>
<p>Question 1.7 What policies are currently in place to ensure high quality data and to what extent are these policies formalised?</p>
<p>Question 1.8 What metrics/KPIs or standards are being utilised to measure data quality, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent are these measures objective?</p>

¹ Users may utilise the DAMA NL Dimensions of Data Quality (Van Nederpelt & Black, 2020; Werkgroep Data Kwaliteit DAMA NL, 2023) for guidance, via <https://dama-nl.org/dimensions-of-data-quality-en/>

2nd Dimension - Privacy and Security

The **Privacy and Security**-dimension refers to those methods and practices undertaken by the organisation to ensure all data is kept secure and confidential. It concerns both technical and non-technical methods and practices to ensure all data is secure and shielded from unintended parties.

Question 2.1a

What domains, datasets, data sources and systems require the most extensive privacy and security measures?

Question 2.1b

To what extent can the privacy and security of data within these domains, datasets, data sources and systems be guaranteed?

Question 2.2

To what extent and in what way does the current state of data classification influence privacy and security-related issues?

Question 2.3

Do data breaches happen often, are they documented and to what extent are they being used as inputs for preventive solutions?

Question 2.4

To what extent are authorisations provided based on (formal) policies and to what extent are authorisations frequently actualised?

Question 2.5

To what extent is sensitive data encrypted and/or shielded from unauthorised parties?

Question 2.6

What policies and/or standards are currently in place to ensure adequate privacy and security measures are taken and to what extent are these formalised?

Question 2.7

What (technical) processes are currently in place to ensure the necessary privacy and security standards are met and to what extent are these formalised?

3rd Dimension - Risk and Compliance

In this dimension, **Risk** refers to the processes by which data security risks are identified, qualified, quantified, rejected, accepted, and/or mitigated in an organisation.

In this dimension, **Compliance** refers to the efforts of an organisation, concerning its data management/governance, to ensure relevant legislation is complied with.

Question 3.1

What, if any, legislation is of central importance to the organisation and its core business and to what extent can compliance be guaranteed based on data management practices?

Question 3.2

To what extent and in what way does the current state of data classification influence issues within risk management and compliance-related issues?

Question 3.3

To what extent are data management practices aligned with risk management and to what extent do data management practices reinforce risk management?

Question 3.4

What (technical) processes are currently in place to ensure compliance with legislation and to enhance risk management and to what extent are these formalised?

Question 3.5

What policies are currently in place to ensure compliance with legislation and sound risk management and to what extent are these formalised?

4th Dimension - Data Access and Usage

In this dimension, **Data Access** concerns those methods, practices, systems and processes within the organisation that arrange and coordinate requesting, providing and gaining access to data.

In this dimension, **Data Usage** concerns those methods, practices and processes within the organisation that serve to coordinate the usage of data by data recipients/users.

Question 4.1a

Is there a formalised process in place for requesting/providing data access for both internal and external stakeholders?

Question 4.1b

To what extent does this process meet privacy & security and risk & compliance standards?

Question 4.2

To what extent is the current state of requesting data, providing/obtaining it and subsequently using it deemed satisfactory by all stakeholders involved? (i.e. how does it currently 'perform'?)

Question 4.3

To what extent and in what way does the current state of data classification influence the current state of data access and usage?

Question 4.4

Is there a dedicated system for internal and external data transmissions and to what extent can this system guarantee privacy & security and risk & compliance standards are met?

Question 4.5

Are data sharing agreements (DSA's) made as a means to guide the reciprocal relationship between data recipients and providers and to what extent are these DSA's formalised?

5th Dimension - People and Culture

The **People and Culture**-dimension concerns human factors and organisational culture, the latter mostly determined by human factors, related to the organisation's data management practices.

This dimension mostly aims to establish how the organisation generally values data and its management/governance and how the organisation approaches 'managing people'

Question 5.1

What is your assessment of the awareness of the importance of data, data quality and data management throughout the entire organisation? (e.g. from operational to executive level)

Question 5.2

What is your assessment of the 'data literacy' throughout the entire organisation?

Data literacy here means the overall capability to understand data, work with it, communicate about it and argue based on it (Gartner, 2021). As an example, a data literate person (not working within the data management capability) can read and understand a common table, communicate about it with peers and also argue based on it. This essentially implies the capacity of turning data into information.

Question 5.3

To what extent is there a conscious management style within data management practices? (e.g. bottom-up vs. top-down, participative vs. directive)

Question 5.4

To what extent is there a conscious approach when functions or roles need to be filled? (e.g. searching for intrinsically motivated role-fulfillers vs. assigning roles)

Question 5.5

What metrics/KPIs are being utilised to manage people, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent are these measures objective?

Question 5.6

What processes and/or policies are in place to enhance the popularity of data management practices and to support data enthusiasts and to what extent are these formalised?

6th Dimension - Ownership Model Design Choices

The **Ownership Model Design Choices**-dimension concerns the designing of the ownership model as a formal organisational model for ownership model practices. This includes, but is not limited to, forming role or function names, establishing their responsibilities, drawing the actual model and so forth.

Question 6.1

To what extent has an ownership model been designed and implemented and to what extent is this model formalised?

Use the current state of the ownership model as a foundation to further build upon during the following questions.

Question 6.2

To what extent has a conscious design choice been made regarding the scope of the ownership model? (e.g. according to subject area, business domain, applications/systems, business processes, etc. (Polsky, 2013; van Gils, 2020)).

Question 6.3

Your assessment of all prior questions should indicate what central ownership model accountabilities, responsibilities and activities are currently present, which are not and to what extent they are formalised.

Based on this assessment, to what extent are these accountabilities, responsibilities and activities already being fulfilled by agents and to what extent are the roles and/or functions these agents fulfil formalised?²

Question 6.4

Based on your assessment of all prior questions, what, if any, ownership model roles and/or functions that are not yet present are deemed necessary to fulfil the established central accountabilities, responsibilities and activities?

Question 6.5a

Is there a decision-making body involved in data management/governance decision-making that includes representatives from across the entire organisation?

Question 6.5b

To what extent has this decision-making body been formalised?

Question 6.6a

To what extent is it clear for the agents fulfilling the roles and/or functions within the ownership model what they can and cannot expect or demand from each other?

Question 6.6b

To what extent has the former been formalised?

² Users may utilise RACI or RASCI-matrices as a tool to divide and visualise the distribution of accountabilities, responsibilities and activities among the different roles and/or functions.

7th Dimension - Prerequisites

The *Prerequisites*-dimension refers to factors or conditions that need to be met, at least to some extent, for ownership model implementations to succeed.

This implies that ownership model implementations can still succeed when one or more prerequisites have not or have only partially been met. However, not meeting these prerequisites gravely lowers the chance for successful ownership model implementations.

Question 7.1

What is your assessment of the executive-level endorsement of data management and governance practices and is data generally seen as an asset by executives?

Question 7.2

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent does the current state and intended future state of the ownership model guarantee executive-level endorsement of data management and governance practices?

Question 7.3

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent is the current state and intended future state of the ownership model in line with the organisation's strategy, vision and general (non-data related) policies?

Question 7.4

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent is the current state and intended future state of the ownership model in line with the overall Data Management Framework and Data Governance Framework?

Question 7.5

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent do the current state and intended future state of the ownership model guarantee the cultivation of a data culture within the organisation?

Ownership Model Implementation Tool (OMIT) - Instruction Sheet

Objectives:

The OMIT aims to enable organisations to 1) reflect on the current state of ownership model practices, 2) to provide guidance in establishing a roadmap towards an intended future state and 3) to ensure that crucial ownership model dimensions have been considered.

Target audience:

The OMIT is targeting data management professionals that aim to fulfil one or more of the OMIT-objectives. These may be data management professionals internal to an organisation or external professionals, like consultants. These professionals are likely to have multiple years of experience in data management/governance. Moreover, using the OMIT likely requires the involvement and collaboration of multiple stakeholders from various departments.

Instructions:

- Users are advised to browse through the entire tool beforehand as some of the final questions relate to prior questions.
- Answering the questions should be done as detailed and complete as possible. This potentially takes a considerable amount of time and, as was mentioned before, will likely require the collaboration of multiple stakeholders within the organisation.
- Users may encounter difficulties while answering certain questions due to a lacking presence of certain topics within the organisation. In this case, users are advised to bear in mind that the questions are also meant to provide guidance in establishing a roadmap. The topics within questions can therefore also be seen as central topics within establishing an intended future state.
- If the user finds this suitable, the OMIT questions can easily be transformed to suite a Likert scale-style measure. Examples of this are scoring questions as follows:
 1. very low/none **OR** very little/none **OR** (almost) never
 2. low **OR** little **OR** sometimes
 3. average **OR** occasionally
 4. high **OR** much **OR** usually
 5. very high **OR** very much **OR** (almost) always

For inspiration, users may find Marchildon et al. (2018) useful. In doing so, organisations might find it easier to establish a current state and work towards an intended future state.

Additional advice:

- Users are advised to use the OMIT in conjunction with other practical (assessment) tools, like data governance maturity tools, to enhance the holisticness of the resulting ownership model.
- There is a plethora of different terminologies and wording when it comes to data governance and ownership model practices. To partially address this, definitions have been provided for each dimension to ensure users are aware of the implied semantics in the OMIT. However, users should be aware that while utilising the OMIT in conjunction with other practical tools, terminology and/or wording may differ and should be regarded with care.

Appendix B - 2nd version of the OMIT

Introduction

The statement that data is of grave importance to organisations and that effective usage can yield large advantages is far from new and, hence, recognised widely. Following this, the amount of data collected and utilised by organisations is ever-growing. This ongoing trend has emphasised the need for proper management and governance of data, as is further recognised by a growing number of organisations that are formally incorporating data governance structures into the organisation.

Popular among these data governance structures is the usage of data ownership models. A data ownership model, or ownership model, is an organisational model that serves to coordinate data management, maintenance and usage. An example of such a model can be seen in the figure below, based on van Gils (2020) ¹.

Example of a data ownership model (taken from van Gils (2020) ¹).

A data ownership model uses the assignment of roles to people within the organisation as a basis for coordinative actions. Roles that are generally though not exclusively found are 'Data Owners', 'Data Stewards' and 'Data Users'. The fulfillers of these roles, in turn, have certain accountabilities, responsibilities and activities within the organisation's data management/governance capability (van Gils, 2020). If formalised, this role-based model generally depicts lines connecting the different roles to indicate the primary interaction between agents while fulfilling their roles, as seen in the figure.

While organisations are increasingly incorporating data governance structures, like data ownership models, only few practical tools are readily available for data management professionals and organisations to be used during the design and implementation of such data ownership models. Against this background, a practical tool called 'Ownership Model Implementation Tool' (OMIT) was developed to better enable organisations in designing and implementing a data ownership model.

¹ van Gils, B. (2020). *Data Management: A gentle introduction: Balancing theory and practice*. Van Haren.

What is the intended use of the OMIT?

The OMIT is a practical tool to be used during the design, implementation and (further) improvement of an organisational data ownership model. The OMIT aims to:

- 1) Enable organisations to reflect on the current state of data ownership model practices
- 2) Provide guidance in establishing a 'roadmap' or list with areas for improvement that aim to work towards an intended future state of data ownership model practices
- 3) Ensure that crucial data ownership model dimensions and aspects have been considered and addressed appropriately

The OMIT consists of 7 crucial dimensions, shown in the table below, that need to be considered by organisations when addressing their data ownership model. Each dimension has a certain amount of questions that allow self-assessment of the organisation along the crucial data ownership model dimensions.

Central ownership model dimensions in the OMIT	
1. Data Quality and Integrity	2. Confidentiality and Security
3. Risk and Compliance	4. Data Access and Usage
5. People and Culture	6. Ownership Model Design Choices
7. Prerequisites	

Who is the OMIT intended for?

The OMIT is targeting data management professionals that aim to fulfil one or more of the aforementioned objectives. These may be data management professionals internal to an organisation or external professionals, like consultants who are helping an organisation in establishing a data ownership model. Depending on the size of the organisation, these professionals are likely situated within or are often consulting with the higher hierarchical levels of the organisation. Professionals using the OMIT are expected to have multiple years of experience in data management/governance.

Likely, the necessary knowledge to make a full assessment with the OMIT is dispersed across the organisation, depending on the size of the organisation. As such, using the OMIT likely requires the involvement and collaboration of multiple stakeholders from various departments.

How to use the OMIT

The questions within each of the 7 dimensions are consciously formulated in a rather broad manner. The aim of this is to provoke a broad thought process regarding the content of the questions, aiming to yield an overview as complete as possible. Answers will therefore be qualitative and will be extensive in size. This implies that answering the questions should be done as detailed and complete as possible. This potentially takes a considerable amount of time and, as was mentioned before, will likely require the collaboration of multiple stakeholders within the organisation.

Answers that have been formulated can, later on, serve as a benchmark for establishing what data ownership model aspects are areas for improvement. This should help to formulate what topics an organisation can/should address to achieve an intended future state for data ownership model practices.

Instructions and additional advice

- Users are advised to browse through the entire tool upfront as some of the latter questions relate to earlier questions.
- Users may encounter difficulties while answering certain questions due to a lacking presence of certain topics within the organisation. This is a direct result of the consciously broad formulation of questions within the OMIT. Users should bear in mind that the topics within questions are also meant to provoke broad thinking and are meant to provide guidance in establishing areas for improvement. If specific topics or aspects are not or are only very limitedly present, this could indicate a potential area for improvement.
- If the user finds this suitable, the OMIT questions can easily be transformed to allow a Likert scale answer. This implies that questions are not qualitatively answered but are instead scored on a scale of 1 to 5 indicating the level of presence of an aspect within the organisation. For questions to be answerable in this manner, slight reformulations are necessary ².

Consider question 1.8 as an example. First, the question should be pulled apart: *“Are metrics/KPIs or standards being utilised to measure data quality?”*, *“To what extent are these metrics/KPIs formalised?”* and *“To what extent are these measures objective?”*.

Second, the question should be reformulated so that the most appropriate answering option can then be filled in, like *“Metrics/KPIs are ... utilised to measure data quality.* Considering the following examples of possible Likert scale answer options, questions could then be answered as follows:

	Possible Likert scale measures ²				
Option 1	very low/none	low	Average	High	Very high
Option 2	very little/none	little	Average	Much	Very much
Option 3	(almost) never	sometimes	Occasionally	Usually	(almost) always

Here the answer ‘never’ implies the lowest level (1) and the answer ‘always’ implies the highest level (5). Scores of individual questions can then be aggregated and averaged per dimension to yield a maturity level per dimension. By doing so, organisations might find it easier to establish a concrete maturity level of current data ownership model practices to be used as a point of reference now and in further development of the data ownership model.

- Users are advised to use the OMIT in conjunction with other practical (assessment) tools, like data governance maturity tools, to enhance the holisticness of the resulting data ownership model.
- There is a plethora of different terminologies and wording when it comes to data governance and data ownership model practices. To partially address this, definitions have been provided for each dimension to ensure users are aware of the implied semantics in the OMIT. However, users should be aware that while utilising the OMIT in conjunction with other practical tools, terminology and/or wording may differ and should be regarded with care.

² For inspiration on how to re-formulate questions and what Likert scale measures to use, users may find Marchildon et al. (2018) useful, via Marchildon, P., Bourdeau, S., Hadaya, P., & Labissière, A. (2018). Data governance maturity assessment tool: A design science approach. *Projectics/Proyèctica/Projectique*, (2), 155-193.

Ownership Model Implementation Tool (OMIT)

1st Dimension - Data Quality and Integrity
<p>In this dimension, Data Quality concerns those methods and practices undertaken by the organisation to ensure all data meets certain quality standards, based on predefined requirements and data quality dimensions (for a clarification of data quality dimensions, please refer to ³).</p> <p>In this dimension, Data Integrity concerns the organisational efforts in ensuring accurate and consistent data that can be placed into context, the latter indicating the importance of metadata. By all data, we mean data from all sources and in all content formats.</p>
<p>Question 1.1a To what extent have data quality dimensions been established that are essential for the organisation? (for a clarification of data quality dimensions, please refer to ⁵).</p>
<p>Question 1.1b To what extent are data quality dimensions and targeted data quality levels tailored to fit specific situations in which data is needed?</p>
<p>Question 1.2 To what extent and in what way has (essential) data been classified to support data quality management and how does this current state of data classification influence data quality issues?</p>
<p>Question 1.3 What datasets and source systems/golden sources are crucial for the organisation's core business and management information and to what extent do these exhibit data quality issues?</p>
<p>Question 1.4 Are data quality issues documented and to what extent are they used as inputs for solutions?</p>
<p>Question 1.5 What (technical and operational) processes and measures are currently in place to address and improve data quality and to what extent are these processes formalised?</p>
<p>Question 1.6 To what extent is data/business modelling deployed (i.e. establishing a conceptual model with definitions and interrelationships) and has a data glossary, catalogue or dictionary been made?</p>
<p>Question 1.7 To what extent is reference data being utilised and to what extent is this reference data being maintained and actualised in an organised manner?</p>
<p>Question 1.8 What policies are currently in place to address and improve data quality and to what extent are these policies formalised?</p>
<p>Question 1.9 What metrics/KPIs or standards are being utilised to measure data quality, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent are these measures objective?</p>

⁵ Users may find the DAMA NL Dimensions of Data Quality (Van Nederpelt & Black, 2020; Werkgroep Data Kwaliteit DAMA NL, 2023) useful for clarification and may utilise these for guidance in establishing data quality dimensions, via <https://dama-nl.org/dimensions-of-data-quality-en/>

2nd Dimension - Confidentiality and Security

The **Confidentiality and Security** dimension refers to those methods and practices undertaken by the organisation to ensure sensitive data is kept secure and confidential, including privacy-related practices. It concerns both technical and non-technical methods and practices to ensure sensitive data is secure and shielded from unintended parties.

Question 2.1a

What domains, datasets, data sources and systems require the most extensive confidentiality and security measures?

Question 2.1b

To what extent can the confidentiality and security of data within these domains, datasets, data sources and systems be guaranteed?

Question 2.2

To what extent and in what way has (essential) data been classified to support confidentiality and security measures and in what way does the current state of data classification influence confidentiality and security-related issues?

Question 2.3

What is your assessment of the frequency and severity of data breaches, are data breaches documented and to what extent are they being used as inputs for preventive solutions?

Question 2.4

To what extent are authorisations provided based on (formal) policies and to what extent are authorisations frequently actualised?

Question 2.5

To what extent are methods and/or measures deployed to shield sensitive data from unauthorised parties?

Concrete examples of methods to shield sensitive data from unauthorised parties are encryption, firewalls, multifactor authentication, physical security measures and so forth. Examples of industry standards within the confidentiality and security domain potentially relevant to establish these methods and/or measures are versions of the NIST 800 standards and ISO/IEC 27001.

Question 2.6

To what extent are only specific parts of datasets and/or records designated to be subject to confidentiality and security measures, considering both primary- and secondary-used data?

Question 2.7

What policies and/or standards are currently in place to ensure adequate confidentiality and security measures are taken, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent have both primary- and secondary-used data been considered?

It should be clear that organisational policies and standards are different from the aforementioned industry standards (i.e. NIST-800 and ISO/IEC 27001), even though these industry standards can potentially serve as a foundation for organisational policies and standards.

Question 2.8

What (technical) processes are currently in place to ensure the necessary confidentiality and security standards are met, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent have both primary- and secondary-used data been considered?

3rd Dimension - Risk and Compliance

In this dimension, **Risk** refers to the methods and processes by which data-related risks are identified, qualified, quantified, rejected, accepted, and/or mitigated in an organisation. These methods and processes do not only concern data security risks but also concern broader organisational risks for which adequate data management is of central importance.

An example of such a broad organisational risk that is still data management related could be financial risks that are identified, prevented and/or caused by inaccurate data and, therefore potentially, inadequate data management.

In this dimension, **Compliance** refers to the efforts of an organisation, concerning its data management/governance, to ensure relevant legislation is complied with.

Question 3.1

What, if any, legislation is of central importance to the organisation and its core business and to what extent can compliance be guaranteed based on data management practices?

Question 3.2

To what extent and in what way has (essential) data been classified to support risk and compliance measures and in what way does the current state of data classification influence risk and compliance-related issues?

Question 3.3

To what extent are data management practices aligned with overall organisational risk management and to what extent do data management practices reinforce overall organisational risk management?

Question 3.4

To what extent are (security) risk assessments conducted within the data management domain and to what extent do these risk assessments determine the undertaken pre-emptive measures?

Question 3.5

What (technical) processes are currently in place to ensure compliance with legislation and to enhance risk management and to what extent are these formalised?

Question 3.6

What policies are currently in place to ensure compliance with legislation and sound risk management and to what extent are these formalised?

Question 3.7

To what extent have the potential effects for data management practices of changes in legislation been anticipated pre-emptively?

4th Dimension - Data Access and Usage

In this dimension, **Data Access** concerns those methods, practices, systems and processes within the organisation that arrange and coordinate the access to certain desired data. This includes both the user's and supplier's side of gaining and facilitating access to the desired data. In this dimension, **Data Usage** concerns those methods, practices and processes within the organisation that serve to coordinate the usage of data by data recipients/users.

Question 4.1a

Is there a formalised process in place for facilitating data access for both internal and external stakeholders?

What is meant here, is the entire process from the moment a potential user of data takes action to be able to use the data until the moment that user starts using the data. This includes potential intermediary processes of data preparation and making it available/forwarding it.

Question 4.1b

To what extent does this process meet confidentiality & security and risk & compliance standards?

Question 4.1c

To what extent is the route of the data through this process and the mutations along the way traceable and to what extent is this process transparent for others?

Question 4.1d

Related to question 4.1c, to what extent does this process consider traceability and transparency of secondary-used data?

Question 4.2

Is there a dedicated system for internal and external data sharing and to what extent can this system guarantee confidentiality & security and risk & compliance standards are met?

Question 4.3

To what extent and in what way has (essential) data been classified to support the process of data access and usage and in what way does the current state of data classification influence related issues?

Question 4.4

To what extent is the current state of requesting data, providing/obtaining it and subsequently using it deemed satisfactory by all stakeholders involved? (i.e. how does it currently 'perform'?)

Question 4.5a

Are data sharing agreements (DSAs) made as a means to guide the reciprocal relationship between data recipients and providers and to what extent are these DSAs formalised?

Question 4.5b

To what extent is the current way of working with DSAs deemed satisfactory by all stakeholders involved and what is your assessment of how well this way of working currently performs?

'Way of working with DSAs', implies everything related to the process of creating, logging and enacting the DSAs as well as the content, form and format of the DSAs.

5th Dimension - People and Culture

The **People and Culture** dimension concerns human factors and organisational culture, the latter mostly determined by human factors, related to the organisation's data management practices.

This dimension mostly aims to establish how the organisation generally values data and its management/governance and how the organisation approaches 'managing people'.

Question 5.1

What is your assessment of the 'data literacy' throughout the entire organisation?

Data literacy means the overall capability to understand and work with, communicate about and argue based on data (Gartner, 2021 ⁴). For example, a data literate person (not working within data management) can read and understand a common table, communicate about it with peers and also argue based on it. This essentially implies the capacity of turning data into information.

Question 5.2

What is your assessment of the awareness of the importance of data, data quality and data management throughout the entire organisation? (e.g. from operational to executive level)

Question 5.3

To what extent is there a conscious approach or management style for data management practices that affect people within the organisation? (e.g. bottom-up vs. top-down, collaborative vs. directive, command & control vs. non-invasive)

'A conscious approach' implies that the organisation's culture and the current and intended future data management/governance maturity level have been considered.

Question 5.4

To what extent is there a conscious approach when functions or roles need to be filled? (e.g. searching for intrinsically motivated role-fulfillers vs. assigning roles)

Roles and/or functions that are generally found in a data ownership model were mentioned in the introduction. Examples are Data Owner, Data Steward, Data User, Data Custodian and any of the above combined with a title such as executive, chief, technical, business, coordinating and so on. The specific name of the roles or functions, however, often differs widely per organisation.

'A conscious approach' implies that the organisation's culture and the current and intended future data management/governance maturity level have been considered.

Question 5.5a

What metrics/KPIs are being utilised to manage people, to what extent are these formalised and to what extent are these measures objective?

Question 5.5b

To what extent are these metrics/KPIs designed and used to facilitate the personal and functional development of people?

Question 5.6

What processes and/or policies are in place to enhance the popularity of data management practices and to support data enthusiasts and to what extent are these formalised?

⁴ Gartner. (2021, August). *A Data and Analytics Leader's Guide to Data Literacy*. Retrieved January 10, 2023, from <https://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/a-data-and-analytics-leaders-guide-to-data-literacy>

6th Dimension - Data Ownership Model Design Choices

The **Data Ownership Model Design Choices** dimension concerns the designing of the data ownership model as a formal organisational model that serves to coordinate data management, maintenance and usage (refer to the introduction for a clarification of 'data ownership model'). The questions below address the central design choices when developing, implementing and/or improving a data ownership model and aim to guide organisations in doing so.

Question 6.1

To what extent has a data ownership model been designed and implemented and to what extent is this model formalised?

Use the current state of the data ownership model as a foundation to further build upon during the following questions.

Question 6.2

To what extent has a conscious design choice been made regarding the scope of the data ownership model? (e.g. according to subject area, business domain, applications/systems, business processes, etc. (Polsky, 2013⁵; van Gils, 2020¹)).

Question 6.3

Your assessment of all prior questions should indicate what central data ownership model accountabilities, responsibilities and activities are currently present, which are not and to what extent they are formalised.

To what extent has secondary usage of data been considered in establishing these accountabilities and responsibilities, in establishing who is/remains accountable/responsible as data moves through the organisation and to what extent has this been formalised?

Question 6.4

Based on the assessment of all prior questions, to what extent are the central data ownership model accountabilities, responsibilities and activities already being fulfilled by employees and to what extent are the roles and/or functions these employees fulfil formalised? ⁶

Question 6.5

Based on your assessment of all prior questions, what data ownership model roles or functions are not yet present and are deemed necessary to fulfil the established central accountabilities, responsibilities and activities?

Please refer to the introduction and question 5.4 for an example of possible functions and/or roles.

⁵ Polsky, A. (2013). *Data stewardship on the ground, notes from the field* [Presentation at the Data Governance Conference in London].

⁶ Users may utilise RACI or RASCI-matrices as a tool to divide and visualise the distribution of accountabilities, responsibilities and activities among the different roles and/or functions.

Question 6.6a

Is there a decision-making body involved in data management/governance decision-making that includes representatives from across the entire organisation?

Question 6.6b

To what extent has this decision-making body been formalised?

Question 6.7a

To what extent is it clear for employees in data ownership model roles and/or functions what the accountabilities, responsibilities and activities are for each respective role and/or function? (i.e. is it clear to them what can be expected and demanded from each other?)

Question 6.7b

To what extent has the former been formalised?

7th Dimension - Prerequisites

The **Prerequisites** dimension refers to factors or conditions that need to be met, at least to some extent, for data ownership model implementations to succeed.

This implies that data ownership model implementations can still succeed when one or more prerequisites have not or have only partially been met. However, not meeting these prerequisites gravely lowers the chance for successful data ownership model implementations.

Question 7.1a

What is your assessment of the executive-level endorsement of data management/governance practices and is data generally seen as an asset by executives?

Question 7.1b

To what extent does the executive-level endorsement of data management/governance practices resonate in their decisions/actions and in providing mandate for decisions/actions?

Question 7.1c

What is your assessment of the operational-level endorsement of data-related practices and is data generally seen as important at the operational level?

Question 7.2

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent does the current state and intended future state of the data ownership model guarantee executive- and operational-level endorsement of data management/governance practices?

Question 7.3

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent is the current state and intended future state of the data ownership model in line with the organisation's strategy, vision and general (non-data related) policies?

Question 7.4

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent is the current state and intended future state of the data ownership model in line with the overall Data Management Framework and/or Data Governance Framework?

Question 7.5

Based on your assessment of all prior answers, to what extent do the current state and intended future state of the data ownership model guarantee the cultivation of a data culture within

A 'data culture' can be described as the collective beliefs and behaviours of people in an organisation that enable leveraging data as an organisational asset (Southehal, 2022 ⁷). This involves those beliefs and behaviours that reinforce the organisational data literacy and overall endorsement of data management/governance throughout the entire organisation.

(Format, layout and formulation of definitions based on Marchildon et al. (2018 ²))

⁷ Southehal, P. (2022, June). *Data Culture: What It Is And How To Make It Work*. Retrieved March 28, 2023, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2022/06/27/data-culture-what-it-is-and-how-to-make-it-work/>

Appendix C - Code book: phase one interviews

Axial codes

Axial code	Nr. of open codes assigned to the axial code
1. (On)volwassenheid (maturity) van de organisatie op data management/governance gebied	14
2. Uitdagingen/problemen gerelateerd aan Ownership modellen / Governance Frameworks	9
3. Design aspecten van ownership modellen	12
4. Macro organisatie/management aspecten van ownership modellen (organizational control)	6
5. Micro-/Meso organisatie/management aspecten van ownership modellen	7
6. Randvoorwaarden (prerequisites)	3
7. Tasks & Responsibilities van verschillende Data Rollen	8
8. In Vivo Codes - nice illustrative expressions	3

Open codes

Open code	Nr. of text-fragments to which code was assigned	Nr. of axial code to which open code was assigned
(on)beschikbaarheid van middelen voor uitvoeren data governance activiteiten (resource allocation)	21	2, 5, 6
Aanwezigheid formeel governance board of afdeling voor governance activiteiten	7	1, 3
Afwezigheid formeel governance board of afdeling voor governance activiteiten.	4	1, 3
Afwezigheid formeel ownership model en data processen leidt tot problemen	3	2
Aligning managen van 'data as an asset'	20	4
Andere rollen binnen ownership model dan Data Owner	19	3
Data Owner rol binnen ownership modellen	27	3
Data actualisatie uitvoeren	3	7
Data classificeren	12	7
Data consistentie creëren (technisch & semantisch)	35	7
Data integratie en interoperabiliteit	11	7
Data Sharing Agreements (DSA's) als onderdeel data accesibility proces	9	3, 5, 7

Data toegang/verspreiding (accessibility) onderhandelen	20	3, 7
Drijfveren voor implementatie ownership modellen	13	X
Gebruik RACI-model voor vastleggen verantwoordelijkheden	10	3
Geen formele functies ontworpen/geïmplementeerd	10	1, 3
Geen formele rollen ontworpen/geïmplementeerd	5	1, 3
Indirecte meetbaarheid/zichtbaarheid van bijdrage data governance activiteiten aan organisatie als geheel	6	2
Inrichting ownership model en/of data management/governance praktijken vanuit enterprise perspectief.	8	2
Inrichting ownership model en/of data management/governance praktijken vanuit siloed perspectief	5	2
Mandaat om personen aan te sturen (hard/soft) binnen data governance activiteiten	21	4
Maturity cross-domain samenwerking en samenspraak	21	1
Maturity data-denken	59	1, 2
Maturity proces/systeem interne data toegang en verspreiding (accessibility)	27	1
Maturity van data beleid	30	1
Maturity van data kwaliteit	25	1
Maturity van data rollen	51	1
Maturity van data werkprocessen/formele activiteiten	28	1
Metten van prestatie d.m.v. metrics / KPI's (subjectief & objectief)	9	5
Participatieve sturing	20	4, 5
Prescriptieve sturing	10	4, 5
Rollen worden bottom-up gezocht	9	4, 5
Rollen worden top-down aangewezen	5	4, 5
Sturen op het begrijpen van data en van het belang van data binnen de gehele organisatie (maturity data-denken).	53	1, 2, 6
Top-down support voor data management/governance activiteiten.	18	6
Uitdagingen/problemen resulterend uit organisatie specifieke kenmerken	11	2
Verantwoordelijk voor privacy en security gerelateerde aspecten.	25	7

Verantwoordelijk voor risk en compliance gerelateerde aspecten.	24	7
Vraagstuk omtrent ownership model categorisatie	11	3
Wel formele functies ontworpen/geïmplementeerd	11	1, 3
Wel formele rollen ontworpen/geïmplementeerd	20	1, 3
Wildgroei aan terminologie en definiëring van functies en functie-inhoud	10	2

In-vivo codes

In-vivo code	Nr. of text-fragments to which code was assigned	Nr. of axial code to which in-vivo code was assigned
"coalition of the willing"	8	8
"data schuld"	7	8
"fear of missing out"	4	8